

31-08-2025

Deliverable D2.2: Report on Robotics education programmes results after the first year of delivery of programmes

Deliverable D2.2

Contractual Date: 31-08-2025
Actual Date: 31-08-2025
Grant Agreement No.: 101123118
Work Package: WP2
Task Item: D2.2
Lead Partner: UNIBO

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Abstract

Report on the annual results achieved by WP2, including reporting on the delivery of the master's programme and self-standing learning modules.

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The activities leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's DIGITAL Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101123118 (SPECTRO).

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Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	10/06/2025	Giuseppe Notarstefano (UNIBO), Francesca Franchi (UNIBO), Davide Brunelli (UNITN), Valeria Giacomoni (UNITN)	First draft
0.2	25/07/2025	Mihhail Matskin (KTH), Zhou Quan (AALTO), Raphaël Troncy (EURECOM), Istenes Zoltan (ELTE), Guillaume Ducard (UCA), Kiss Bálint (BME)	Contributions from partners to the Annex
0.3	05/08/2025	Ivano Notarnicola (UNIBO)	Contributions on self-standing modules
0.4	06/08/2025	Romane Léauté (EITD)	Contributions on admission process and other project-level data
1.0	08/08/2025	Giuseppe Notarstefano (UNIBO), Francesca Franchi (UNIBO), Ivano Notarnicola (UNIBO), Davide Brunelli (UNITN), Valeria Giacomoni (UNITN), Romane Léauté (EITD)	Version 1.0 with complete annexes and more stable draft of online modules
2.0	19/08/2025	Giuseppe Notarstefano (UNIBO), Francesca Franchi (UNIBO), Davide Brunelli (UNITN), Valeria Giacomoni (UNITN), Romane Léauté (EITD)	Version 2.0 with new structure and formatting, descriptions in main sections and updated partner contributions

2.1	22/08/2025	Giuseppe Notarstefano (UNIBO), Francesca Franchi (UNIBO), Davide Brunelli (UNITN), Valeria Giacomoni (UNITN), Romane Léauté (EITD)	Updated descriptions of main sections
2.2	27/08/2025	Giuseppe Notarstefano (UNIBO), Francesca Franchi (UNIBO), Davide Brunelli (UNITN), Valeria Giacomoni (UNITN), Romane Léauté (EITD)	Updated description of main sections, reformatting of annex forms and contributions on summer schools
3.0	28/08/2025	Giuseppe Notarstefano (UNIBO), Francesca Franchi (UNIBO), Davide Brunelli (UNITN), Valeria Giacomoni (UNITN), Romane Léauté (EITD)	Final version

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1 Introduction

The deliverable reports on the main activities carried out during the first year of delivering the education programmes on Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots (AUSIR), including preparation of self-standing online modules and activities devoted to preparing the second year of education programmes. As it will be detailed in the following sections, activities have been carried out smoothly, and students' figures and feedback show that the programme has been successfully implemented. The increasing interest in Robotics themes and the interesting structure of the delivered program, including an Innovation and Entrepreneurship part, have met the appreciation of SPECTRO students. Moreover, the strong experience of the involved universities in delivering education programs has given students a good study environment. The transition to the second year is also proceeding smoothly, thanks to the fact that most of (almost all) the students are on track.

The document is organized into four sections (including this introduction), followed by an annex that provides all the details of the activities carried out at each university. Section 2 summarizes the activities carried out for the implementation of the first year of the AUSIR education programme, including project meetings, admission process, and programme development. Moreover, a summary of the lessons learned is provided, while a detailed treatment for each partner is given in the annex. Section 3 describes the implementation of the self-standing modules with a brief presentation of each course and a preliminary list of figures and feedback. Section 4 describes the two summer schools attended by AUSIR students: "AI-driven cybersecurity", held in Rennes, and "Digital Platforms for Smart Cities", held in Helsinki. Finally, the forms in the Annex, one for each university, provide detailed activities for each partner according to the scheme described in Section 2.1.

2 Report of activities

2.1 Summary Report of Activities

The main activities carried out in this reporting period for the Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots Master program have been devoted to the implementation of the first academic year, a.y. 2024-25, and to the preparation of the new a.y. 2025-26. The activities related to a.y. 2024-25 have been, thus, devoted to: welcoming of the new students, implementation of the courses, Quality Assurance (including support to students and collection of students' feedback) and organization of events. As for activities related to the a.y. 2025-26, they have been mainly devoted to marketing, recruiting and dissemination events, students' enrolment, and possible redesign of some courses in the study plan.

All these activities are described in detail for each University in separate forms provided in the Appendix. Each form is mainly structured according to the following sections:

1. **Classes Calendar** describing the implemented courses
2. **Enrolled Students** describing the main statistics related to enrolled students
3. **Study Plan** describing the main offered courses
4. **Student Progress** showing the current status of the students in terms of taken ECTS
5. **Organized Events** for the Students listing and describing the main events for the SPECTRO students, including welcoming initiatives
6. **Feedback from Students** describing official and informal tools to collect students' feedback on the Master program and its implementation
7. **Marketing, Recruiting and Dissemination Activities** listing and describing the main initiatives implemented to attract new students for the a.y. 2025-26 and to promote the project activities
8. **Lesson Learned** summarizing the main achievements during the first year with the gained know-how that can be useful for the improvement of the program.

In the next subsections a project-level summary of the reported activities is provided, followed by a description of the online modules and of the summer school. Then, a list of reports, one for each project partner, is given in Appendix, structured according to the above sections.

2.2 Video Conferences and Meetings

2024

- Feb 13-14 MSL (Master School) & SPECTRO meeting in Brussels,
- Mar 8 SPECTRO online meeting (AUS-SPECTRO meeting),
- Apr 8 SPECTRO online meeting (AUS-SPECTRO meeting),
- Apr 16-17 MSL & SPECTRO meeting in Valencia,
- May 6 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Jun 10 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Jun 17 EIT Digital- SPECTRO Admin meeting
- Jun 25 MSL & SPECTRO meeting (online),
- Jul 7 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Sep 3 MSL & SPECTRO meeting (online),
- Sep 24 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Oct 3-4 EIT Digital Master School Kick-Off in Riga and MSL meeting,
- Oct 11 SPECTRO-AUSIR meeting on WP2
- Oct 29 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Nov 22 MSL & SPECTRO meeting in Budapest,
- Nov 26 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD),
- Dec 12, EIT Digital – SPECTRO Admin meeting

2025

- January 21 SPECTRO online meeting (CSES, AUS, EITD)
- January 24 MSL MGMT & SPECTRO Lead online meeting
- January 27 SPECTRO meeting on scholarships (with WP3)
- January 28 SPECTRO General Assembly online meeting
- January 31 First EITD Master School Communication & Dissemination meeting
- February 20 EIT Digital – SPECTRO Admin meeting
- February 24 MSL & SPECTRO online meeting.
- February 27/28 SPECTRO General Assembly of partners in person, EURECOM, Biot, FRANCE
- March 10 SPECTRO- AUSIR First period applicants Evaluation meeting
- March 14 SPECTRO Interim review rehearsal online meeting
- March 26 SPECTRO interim review meeting with the European Commission Project officer in Budapest, HUNGARY
- March 27 The SPECTRO meeting of consortium partners in Budapest, HUNGARY
- April 8-9 MSL & SPECTRO Meeting, IMDEA Software Institute, Madrid, SPAIN
- April 11 EIT Digital – SPECTRO Admin meeting
- April 29 SPECTRO Monthly WP3 online meeting - Marketing & dissemination
- April 29 SPECTRO PEC (Project Executive Committee) online meeting
- May 6 SPECTRO– AUSIR Second period applicants evaluation meeting
- May 23 SPECTRO meeting on deliverable D2.2
- May 27 SPECTRO Monthly WP3 online meeting - Marketing & dissemination
- May 27 SPECTRO PEC (Project Executive Committee) online meeting
- June 11 SPECTRO consortium online meeting of partners pre-summer (on reporting)
- June 16 SPECTRO– AUSIR Third period applicants Evaluation meeting
- June 17 MSL MGMT & SPECTRO online meeting
- June 23 SPECTRO updates online meeting with the European Commission Project Officer
- July 29 SPECTRO Monthly WP3 online meeting - Marketing & dissemination
- August 7 SPECTRO deliverable D2.2 updates
- August 19 SPECTRO meeting D1.2 and D2.2 review

2.3 SPECTRO Robotics Programme (AUSIR) Admission Process

The admission and scholarship allocation process for the Robotics Master Programme has been described in Deliverable D2.1, Section 3, and will not be repeated here. Readers are invited to consult that section for full details on eligibility criteria, selection procedures, and admission requirements. The Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 admission processes have been conducted according to the D2.1 guidelines agreed by the SPECTRO consortium. Similarly, the application timeline and scholarship allocation framework are outlined in other project deliverables: for Cycle 1 (2024–2026), these details are provided in Deliverable D4.4, while for Cycle 2 (2025–2027), they are included in Deliverable D4.5.

2.3.1 Cycle 1 (2024-2026): Enrolment figures

This subsection presents a summary overview of the Cycle 1 enrolment figures for the SPECTRO Robotics Master’s programme. For a detailed analysis on admissions and scholarships allocation, please refer to Deliverable 4.4.

For Cycle 1 of the SPECTRO Autonomous Systems Master Programme, a total of 206 applications were received, with 36 from EU candidates and 170 from non-EU applicants. Ultimately, 59 students were enrolled—25 from the EU and 34 from outside the EU. Scholarship allocation reports 23 scholarships granted. Gender distribution shows that 46 of the enrolled students are males and 13 females, indicating some improvement in diversity compared to typical STEM programmes. 5 female students received a scholarship. Regional analysis reveals a strong predominance of students from non-RIS countries, accounting for 55 of the 59 enrolments. However, all 4 RIS-countries students who enrolled to the programme received a scholarship. Nationality data highlights significant concentration from China, which alone accounts for 26 students among non-EU enrolments, and Italy, which contributes with 13 students among EU enrolments.

2.3.2 Cycle 2 (2025-2027): Enrolment trends

For an overview on trends related to SPECTRO’s second intake, please refer to Deliverable 4.5.

2.4 Programme Development

The first-year activities of the Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots (AUSIR) program in each partner university is described in detail in the Annex. Overall, the main activities have involved welcoming events of new students, support to students during the academic year, organization of events and initiatives and collection of students’ feedback. Universities have relied on existing programs, but thanks to the project activities ad-hoc events and supporting initiatives have been organized for SPECTRO students, as indicated in the reports of each partner institution. For example, dedicated EIT-labelled events have been organized with a special focus on the AUSIR SPECTRO program including the Innovation and Entrepreneurship themes. Also, some universities have organized specific welcoming sessions dedicated to SPECTRO students. As for feedback from students, questionnaires are anonymous and collected at degree level, thus it was not possible to have separate statistics involving only SPECTRO students for the official partner institution statistics. Yet,

informal feedback from students was collected in some institutions, which revealed a substantial appreciation of students for the AUSIR program. This is consistent with data collected on the students' progress which show that, except for few isolated cases, the enrolled students have achieved the required number of credits and have moved to the next academic year in the exit university.

2.5 Lesson Learned from Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)

A detailed summary of the lessons learned by each partner in this first academic year is reported in the partners' forms. Overall, all the partners reported a satisfaction of the students for the delivered program, which is definitely encouraging for the follow up of this innovative education program. Also, some partners report an increasing interest in the area of Autonomous Systems and Robotics which is confirmed by the recruiting activities for the next year. In some cases, the harmonization of local administration procedures with the common rules of the SPECTRO program has needed some interaction with the project coordinator and among the partners, but the collaboration among partners has smoothly addressed all the related points. Another important feature highlighted by the partner universities is that SPECTRO students have actively integrated with students of the standard programs, thus enriching the existing programs in terms of variety of students' background. Activities for students (as, e.g., welcoming events or recruiting initiatives) have took advantage from existing programs in each local institution, but the SPECTRO project has carried over additional specific initiatives that have increased the offer at each local university. Thanks to the first-year experience, these initiatives have also given suggestions to improve the project dissemination, as suggested by some partners. Moreover, the recruiting activities for 2025-26 have benefited from the first-year program implementation both at administrative level and in terms of recruiting initiatives.

3 Self-standing Learning Modules in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots

3.1 Report on the evolution since 2024

Since 2024, the self-standing learning modules initiative has undergone significant progress, both in terms of content development and platform integration. The majority of the initially envisioned modules have now been fully designed, implemented, and published on the ICARUS platform. We report here only the modules for the Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots (AUSIR) program, while the Innovation and Entrepreneurship courses are provided in Deliverable D1.2 and are not repeated here.

As of August 2025, the catalogue of self-standing modules includes **11 fully-developed courses** tailored specifically for the AUSIR curriculum. These modules cover a wide range of advanced and interdisciplinary topics, including robotics, autonomous systems, and artificial intelligence, with practical applications in sectors such as agriculture and healthcare.

Each course has been carefully designed to support self-paced, online learning and is delivered through an open enrolment model, ensuring accessibility to a global audience of learners. The modules are structured to promote hands-on engagement, with a mix of video content, quizzes and exercises, case studies, and assessment tools, all aligned with current research and industry trends.

The modules are organized in two categories: entry and advanced levels.

By completing the self-standing online learning modules, two types of certificates can be earned:

- Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots - Basics Certificate can be obtained by a student that completes Foundations of Autonomous Systems - plus two other courses from the Entry level modules and one module on I&E.
- Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots - Advanced Certificate can be obtained by a student that completes 3 courses from the Advanced modules plus one module on I&E.

Altogether, the modules should cover at least 30 learning hours to receive a certificate, and the quizzes should be completed with 100% success rate (retake is possible).

3.2 Current status

The Robotics self-standing modules are published online on the [SPECTRO Icarus digital learning platform](#), and they are also published on the Digital Skills and Jobs Platform (DSJP).

The Innovation and Entrepreneurships (I&E) modules have been developed jointly between WP1 and WP2. To avoid unnecessary duplicates, they have only been reported in D1.2 and will not be repeated here. Readers are invited to consult D1.2 to read the report in I&E modules.

The following table contains the name of the Robotics modules and their publication status update.

Entry Level modules (A)	Partner	Status
Introduction to Computer Vision	BME	Online
Introduction to Industrial Robotics	BME	Online
Introduction to Software Engineering Methods	KTH	Online
Principles of Artificial Intelligence	ELTE	Online
Advanced modules (B)		
Miniaturised Robots and Micromanipulation	AALTO	Online
Autonomous Multi-Agent Systems	KTH	Online
Artificial Intelligence for Intelligent Robots	ELTE	Online
Distributed Autonomous Systems	UNIBO	Online
Robotics in Healthcare	UNITN	Online
Introduction to Mobile Robotics in Industry	UNITN	Online
Robotics for Agriculture	UNIBO	Online

3.3 Presentation of each course

3.3.1 List of entry courses

The list of the **entry** courses is as follows.

Entry 1. Introduction to Computer Vision

By: BME

Abstract: Computer Vision is one of the primary fields of Artificial Intelligence (AI), aiming to allow machines to interpret complex scenes based on images, videos, or similar structured input data. The aim of this course is to give an overview of the various topics of this vast field, first by introducing traditional computer vision and its methods. In the second part of the course the modern deep learning-based approaches are introduced as well.

Entry 2. Introduction to Industrial Robotics

By: BME

Abstract: This introductory course provides fundamentals about industrial robots used in automated factories. Industrial robots are multi-axis, programmable devices, suitable for a large variety of tasks in virtually all phases of manufacturing, including sorting, packaging, painting, assembly, quality control, logistics, etc. The robots carrying out such tasks are equipped with tools and integrated into robot cells, which are both designed to meet the specifications of the automated manufacturing operation. Successful completion of the lessons of the course allows understanding of a large number of interconnected notions and paradigms used in automated manufacturing based on robot cells.

Entry 3. Introduction to Software Engineering Methods

By: KTH

Abstract: In this course we are going to present a set of methods and techniques used to guide the software development process. The methods and techniques represent both well-established and relatively new approaches and developments in software engineering area. Having passed the course, the attendant should acquire:

- understanding of the most important concepts and the methods in software development
- skills to evaluate and use the most important concepts and methods in software development.

This is a basic course which is oriented toward people who did not study software engineering area previously but may have some experience in developing software. The course does not have specific pre-requisites and is open for a broad audience.

Entry 4. Principles of Artificial Intelligence

By: ELTE

Abstract: This engaging, informative, and hands-on online course introduces fundamental AI concepts, technologies, and applications while emphasizing real-world use cases, comparisons, and ethical considerations. The course is structured into 7 modules, each containing short, focused video lessons with interactive hands-on exercises.

3.3.2 List of advanced courses

The list of the **advanced** courses is as follows.

Advanced 1. Miniaturised Robots and Micromanipulation

By: AALTO

Abstract: This course provides an introduction to miniaturized robotics, featuring concise video lectures and quizzes to provide a foundational overview of micromanipulation techniques and their applications. The course will include 5 short videos and quizzes.

Advanced 2. Autonomous Multi-Agent Systems

By: KTH

Abstract: This course introduces fundamental principles and techniques of Agent Technology, as well as the usage of such techniques for creating autonomous software systems. Central to the course are the concepts of "intelligent agents", as a paradigm for creating autonomous software components, and "multi-agent systems" as a way of providing coordination and communication between individual autonomous software components. The main topics considered in the courses include agent theory and architectures, negotiation, coordination and methods of interoperation in multi-agent systems. The course is oriented toward developers of autonomous systems. It does not have specific pre-requisites and is open for a broad audience.

Advanced 3. Artificial Intelligence for Intelligent Robots

By: ELTE

Abstract: This course explores how AI enables robots to perceive, learn, move, and interact intelligently with the world. It covers key AI technologies used in robotics, including computer vision, machine learning, reinforcement learning, motion planning, and human-robot interaction, with a strong focus on real-world applications and hands-on experimentation.

Advanced 4. Distributed Autonomous Systems

By: UNIBO

Abstract: This module provides a motivating introduction to application domains and scenarios of interest for a novel distributed algorithmic framework in which a team of autonomous systems cooperates to achieve a common goal. Distributed autonomous systems find application in several domains, ranging from data analytics and decision making to smart mobility and mobile robotics. In these domains, large-scale teams of cooperating agents aim at solving optimization, learning, and control problems by local interactions without a central coordinating unit. The module starts from an excursus of the main technology developments leading to the distributed computing paradigm in the Control Systems community. Then, it provides an overview of how problems of interest in decision making, cooperative robotics, and Artificial Intelligence can be cast into a distributed algorithmic framework.

Advanced 5. Robotics in Healthcare

By: UNITN

Abstract: This course provides a comprehensive overview of healthcare robotics. It begins with an introductory module that outlines the various applications of healthcare robotics and explores their historical development. Subsequent modules delve into specific application areas and key technological aspects. In the second module, we examine the essential technologies that enable robotics in healthcare. Modules three through six focus on specific applications, covering surgical robotics, medical imaging robotics, rehabilitative robotics, and assistive robotics in healthcare. Finally, the last module discusses emerging trends and future directions in the field of healthcare robotics.

Advanced 6. Introduction to Mobile Robotics in Industry

By: UNITN

Abstract: This course provides an introduction to the autonomous mobile robots (AMRs) in industrial environments. Participants will first gain an understanding of what mobile robots are and why they are

increasingly relevant to modern industry. The course then explores the core components that enable mobility and autonomy, including sensors and perception systems, navigation technologies, and power and mobility solutions. Key enabling technologies such as the Robot Operating System (ROS), fleet management platforms, and strategies for safe human–robot collaboration in shared workspaces are discussed. Building on these foundations, the course examines application domains such as warehousing and logistics, manufacturing processes, and inspection and maintenance tasks, highlighting real-world examples and current industrial practices. Finally, the course addresses open challenges in adoption, such as safety, scalability, and integration with existing workflows, and presents future trends shaping the evolution of mobile robotics in industry. By the end of the course, participants will have a clear understanding of both the opportunities and limitations of AMRs, equipping them to critically evaluate and implement mobile robotic solutions in industrial contexts.

Advanced 7. Robotics for Agriculture

By: UNIBO

Abstract: This course focuses on new automation technologies used in agriculture. It begins with an overview of the current technologies available on the market, highlighting how they support automation in the field and examining the roadmaps proposed by major industry players to drive the transition toward advanced solutions. It then explores more innovative technologies that are expected to shape the future of agriculture, with a strong emphasis on environmental and economic sustainability, safety, and productivity. The importance of co-designing robotics and farming practices is underlined as a key factor in enabling the development of precision agriculture.

3.4 Preliminary metrics and feedback

The table below presents, for each Robotics module, the number of learners that started the course to date and how many completed it.

Course name	Number of learners that started the course	Number of learners that completed the course
Artificial Intelligence for Intelligent Robots	19	0
Autonomous Multi-Agent Systems	5	0
Distributed Autonomous Systems	1	0
Introduction to Computer Vision	0	0

Course name	Number of learners that started the course	Number of learners that completed the course
Introduction to Industrial Robotics	7	0
Introduction to Mobile Robotics in Industry	3	0
Introduction to Software Engineering Methods	34	0
Miniaturised Robots and Micromanipulation	4	1
Principles of Artificial Intelligence	14	0
Robotics for Agriculture	4	3
Robotics in Healthcare	7	2

- Total learners started: 98
- Total learners completed: 6
- Overall completion rate: 6%

Across the 11 robotics courses, 98 learners enrolled, but only 6 completed their courses—an overall completion rate of about 6.1%. While some courses attracted a higher number of learners, such as Introduction to Software Engineering Methods with 34 participants and Artificial Intelligence for Intelligent Robots with 19, completions remained low overall. This limited progress is partly explained by delays faced by partners in designing and delivering the modules, compounded by staff turnover as noted during the interim review meeting. Although these challenges initially slowed progress, partners have since published the planned courses, bringing delivery back on track and achieving the relevant KPI. Promotion, however, began later than expected, which has limited visibility and uptake so far. To address this, targeted communication campaigns have been launched, including intensified social media promotion over the summer (July–August 2025), aimed at learners seeking to upskill during quieter periods. Additionally, the Basics and Advanced certificates will be actively promoted to encourage learners to progress beyond individual modules and complete full certification tracks. These measures are intended to strengthen the positioning of the robotics portfolio, boost enrolments, and increase completion rates.

4 Summer Schools

In the summer of 2025, SPECTRO students participated in two dedicated Summer Schools that complemented their academic pathway with hands-on, innovation-oriented experiences. Participants could choose between the AI-Driven Cybersecurity Summer School hosted by the University of Rennes from 29 June to 12 July 2025, and the Digital Platforms for Smart Cities Summer School hosted by Aalto University in Helsinki from 11 to 22 August 2025. A total of 40 students attended the Rennes programme and 46 students joined the Helsinki programme, reflecting strong engagement across both topics. These Summer Schools offered specialised knowledge in different fields, together with opportunities for intercultural exchange, networking, and exposure to real-world challenges. This section presents a summary report for the two SPECTRO summer schools.

4.1 AI-Driven Cybersecurity, Rennes (Jun 29–Jul 12, 2025)

4.1.1 Introduction & Context

The SPECTRO–EIT Digital AI-Driven Cybersecurity Summer School took place from June 29 to July 12, 2025, at the EIT Digital Centre in Rennes, France. This fully in-person, two-week intensive is embedded within the SPECTRO master's programme and is structured to merge rigorous technical education with entrepreneurial skills development. The event's mission: support students in converting AI-driven security concepts into viable startups, aligning with EIT Digital's model of challenge-based learning and venture creation.

4.1.2 Participants

A total of 40 students, primarily from the SPECTRO Cybersecurity MSc track along with broader EIT Digital Master School participants, took part. They were selected through a multi-stage recruitment process prioritizing diversity in academic background, gender, and geography, including participants from RIS (Regional Innovation Scheme) countries.

4.1.3 Objectives & Educational Framework

The Summer School aligns with SPECTRO's mission to integrate technical mastery and entrepreneurial readiness. Its objectives include:

1. Mastering advanced cybersecurity techniques, such as AI-powered threat detection, adversarial resilience, and quantum-safe cryptography.
2. Cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset through structured venture development: from ideation to final pitch.
3. Driving interdisciplinary teamwork, pairing students from technical and business streams on challenge-based projects.

4.1.4 Programme Structure & Activities

4.1.4.1 Weekly Agenda

Week 1 (Jun 29–Jul 5):

- Opening sessions, technical lectures, and initial venture-track introductions.
- Team formation and ideation.
- Evening social events including team-building exercises like guided tree-climbing.
- Weekend cultural excursion to Saint-Malo and Mont Saint-Michel.

Week 2 (Jul 6–Jul 12):

- Continuation of venture coaching and prototype incubation.
- An intermediate pitch session offering structured feedback.
- Final pitch day: teams present solutions to an expert jury, with leading teams granted access to a pre-incubator hosted by Rennes Innovation Hub.

4.1.4.2 Technical Lectures & Labs

Students immersed themselves in cutting-edge topics with hands-on components:

- AI-powered threat intelligence: detecting and analyzing advanced cyber threats.
- Adversarial resilience: securing AI models against sophisticated attacks.
- Quantum-safe cryptography: principles of future-proof encryption.

Each lecture combined theory with lab sessions for immediate application.

4.1.4.3 Venture Creation Track

Following a structured three-stage methodology:

- Initial Business Concept (IBC): Teams used templates to map problem–solution scenarios, business models, and technical viability.
- Refinement Coaching: Industry coaches guided market validation, product-market fit, and business logic.
- Final Pitch: Presentations evaluated by a panel of industry experts; top teams moved into an incubator pathway.

4.1.4.4 Keynotes from Industry

The Summer School opened with two keynote sessions delivered by Google Cloud on AI & cybersecurity applications and by Kereval on innovation in AI testing. Subsequent keynotes included:

- INRIA on AI for network security
- University of Rennes (economics faculty) on cyber-economic risk management
- ANSSI on cybersecurity project management

These sessions provided deep corporate and research perspectives connecting AI security and innovation

4.1.4.5 Team-Building & Cultural Activities

Non-academic components included:

- Daily ice-breaking exercises and outdoor challenges
- Social events incorporating local cuisine

- Cultural excursion to iconic historic towns, enhancing community and cross-cultural exchange.

These helped strengthen group cohesion and peer learning.

4.1.5 Outcomes & Metrics

- Attendance: 40 students from diverse institutions completed the full programme.
- Prototype Delivery: Teams formed 10 ventures, with top projects accepted into pre-incubator acceleration in Rennes.
- Student Feedback: High satisfaction scores were registered, particularly about the mix of advanced content and entrepreneurship support.
- Incubator Progress: Winning teams entered local incubation pathways tied to Rennes' innovation ecosystem.

4.1.6 Reflections & Recommendations

Successes:

- Integration of AI and cybersecurity into the core curriculum.
- Effective venture creation framework.
- Strong peer and professional networking.

4.1.7 Alignment with SPECTRO Goals & KPIs

The Summer School advanced multiple strategic targets:

- Strengthened I&E module deployment (KPI6).
- Supported staff and student mobility KPIs (KPI18,19).
- Enhanced innovation pipelines through incubation prep.
- Reinforced programme visibility and recruitment momentum, even amidst earlier communications delays.

4.2 Digital Platforms for Smart Cities, Helsinki (11-22 August 2025)

4.2.1 Introduction and Context

The Digital Platforms for Smart Cities Summer School, hosted at Aalto University in Helsinki from 11–22 August 2025, was part of the EIT Digital Summer School programme. The theme responded to the growing role of digital platforms in transforming businesses, cities, and societies. Today, cities increasingly organise and expose data, which, combined with analytics and machine learning, enhances inclusiveness, engagement, and services for citizens and visitors. Mobility as a service, augmented and virtual reality applications, and intelligent platforms represent just a few examples of how smart city ecosystems are evolving. The Helsinki metropolitan area offered a highly relevant backdrop for this programme, with active engagement from local municipalities, startups, and industrial stakeholders.

4.2.2 Participants

A total of 46 SPECTRO students joined this summer school, representing both the Cybersecurity and Robotics tracks. Together with students from other EIT Digital programmes and young professionals from outside the consortium, they formed a diverse and international cohort. The group engaged in intensive teamwork and also benefited from cultural and social activities organised in Helsinki, fostering intercultural exchanges and networking opportunities.

4.2.3 Objective and Educational Framework

The objective of the programme was to provide participants with entrepreneurial and technical knowledge in digital platforms and smart city innovations. The educational framework combined lectures on platform economies, workshops on digital business models, and applied casework sourced from real-life challenges. Students learned to differentiate between traditional businesses and platforms, to understand the building blocks of multi-sided ecosystems, and to apply concepts of competitiveness and sustainability to digital platforms. Aligned with EIT Digital's Innovation and Entrepreneurship (I&E) model, the framework prioritised venture creation and problem-based learning, ensuring students acquired both conceptual and applied skills.

4.2.4 Programme Structure and Activities

Over two weeks, the programme alternated between thematic lectures, hands-on workshops, and project-based teamwork.

4.2.4.1 *Weekly summative report*

The two-week intensive opened on Monday 11 August with a short welcome by Lea Myyryläinen, orientation logistics, and an indoor team-based game that mixed 50+ participants into balanced teams. After a "lemonade-stand" micro-project used to practise rapid customer discovery, the cohort boarded a 16:15 bus to Seikkailupuisto Huippu adventure park for the first social evening.

Tuesday 12 August was devoted to smart-city thinking. Morning keynotes by Teemu Ropponen ("Cities, People & Data") and Indrajit Chaudhuri ("Product Management of Platforms & Products") were followed by an interview-skills mini-workshop and the first round of domain-expert interviews, setting the cadence of learning-by-doing that would last the whole fortnight.

Wednesday 13 August, starting 30 minutes late, pivoted to data-economy fundamentals. Prof. Marko Turpeinen explored sustainability lenses on data, Erik Liesola delivered the core "Platform Economy Fundamentals" lecture, and the afternoon was reserved for affinity-mapping ideation and project scoping.

Thursday 14 August focused on mobility innovation. Prof. Milos Mladenovic laid out the challenges of smart-mobility innovations, Marco Steinberg gave an architect's view on "Innovation & Design in the Age of Transformation," and the Art-of-Pitching session with Mike prepared teams for their first deliverable.

Friday 15 August mixed FinTech and urban analytics. Monika Liikamaa of Enfuce offered an insider look at payment-platform scaling, Janne Lautanala (Fintraffic) dissected large-scale data for traffic

decisions, and the afternoon was dominated by the midway pitching milestone that doubled as a reality-check and coaching moment.

Weekend 16–17 August was deliberately low on lectures. Saturday was an all-day “Outdoors Day in Natural Park,” giving everyone a breather and informal bonding time; Sunday was left completely free for rest or self-organised sightseeing.

Week two opened Monday 18 August with a deep dive into Aalto University’s entrepreneurship ecosystem. A half-day guided tour of A Grid and the Design Factory replaced formal lectures, while Tomi Paalosmaa’s talk on smart cities and Ohto Pentikäinen’s demo of Doublepoint gesture-control tech kept the technical tempo high. The evening shifted to a quintessential Finnish experience: lakeside sauna and BBQ coupled with a light-hearted “fun-pitch” exercise.

Tuesday 19 August was largely reserved for project sprints—interview prep in the morning and uninterrupted prototyping in the afternoon—punctuated only by Erik Liesola’s session on platform competition and competitive advantage.

Wednesday 20 August moved the cohort to the Viima building and Aalto Design Factory for a full-day hackathon-style build-and-test cycle, supported by Apurva’s validation clinic and Lucy Truong’s alumni fireside chat.

Thursday 21 August was the dress-rehearsal day: pitch coaching, jury Q&A, and final polish sessions ran from early morning until late afternoon, with Olli-Pekka Mutanen locking scope and deliverables.

Friday 22 August closed the programme. Morning final pitching in front of a jury led by Heli Hiden, Tarun Sharma and Natalia was immediately followed by expert-panel feedback, winner announcement, celebratory pizza lunch, and a concise wrap-up that released participants by 15:30.

4.2.4.2 *Technical Lectures & Labs*

Core technical content was delivered in eight compact blocks:

- Smart Cities & Urban Data
- Platform Economy & Competitive Dynamics
- Data Economy & Sustainability
- Smart-Mobility Innovation Challenges
- Product & Platform Management frameworks
- Validation & Prototyping methodologies
- Large-scale Data-Driven Decision Systems
- Gesture & Edge Interfaces

Hands-on labs took place every afternoon: lemonade-stand simulation, affinity-mapping and Crazy-8 ideation, SAM-TAM-SOM market-sizing exercise, rapid-prototyping sprints, and repeated pitch-dry-runs.

4.2.4.3 Keynotes from Industry

High-impact practitioner keynotes anchored each morning:

- Teemu Ropponen – City of Helsinki, “Cities, People & Data”
- Monika Liikamaa – Enfuce Oy, “Scaling a FinTech Platform”
- Janne Lautanala – Fintraffic, “Big Data for Smart Mobility”
- Ohto Pentikäinen – Doublepoint, “Gesture-Control Interfaces”
- Lucy Truong – EIT Digital Alumna, “From Summer School to Series A”

4.2.4.4 Team-Building & Cultural Activities

Structured bonding started on day one with an indoor game and continued outdoors at Seikkailupuisto Huippu. Saturday 16 August offered a full day “Outdoors Day in Natural Park.” The iconic lakeside sauna & BBQ on Monday 18 August blended Finnish culture with a light-hearted “fun-pitch” contest. Informal peer coaching, nightly sauna sessions, and shared meals in Aalto’s campus restaurants completed the cultural immersion, ensuring strong cross-cultural networks that outlast the programme.

4.2.5 Outcomes and Metrics

Students earned 4 ECTS credits upon completion of the summer school. Outcomes were assessed through team project work, final business model pitches, and active participation in lectures and workshops. Programme metrics included 17 hours of dedicated team project development, at least 8 thematic lectures, and engagement with 5 jury members from academia and industry. Participant feedback highlighted the strong relevance of the thematic focus, the high quality of mentoring and coaching, and the value of cultural and networking activities.

4.2.6 Reflections and Recommendations

The summer school successfully delivered on its dual promise of academic learning and entrepreneurial practice. Students particularly appreciated the chance to test their ideas against real-life cases provided by local partners, and to interact with experts from different domains. The cultural programme was equally well received, enabling networking and cohesion across a diverse group of participants. Strengthening links between summer school projects and subsequent master theses or internships was also identified as a valuable next step.

4.2.7 Alignment with SPECTRO Goals and KPIs

The summer school contributed directly to the SPECTRO objectives of fostering student mobility, interdisciplinarity, and exposure to innovation ecosystems. By travelling to Helsinki, SPECTRO

students not only gained credits but also immersed themselves in a new cultural and industrial environment, building their networks and strengthening their entrepreneurial mindset. The activity supports key KPIs related to student mobility, the integration of industry challenges in the academic journey, and engagement with innovation ecosystems.

Annex A to the SPECTRO Report of activities

Deliverable D2.2: Report on Robotics education programme: results after the first year of delivery of programme

A1. Aalto University

Report of activities

Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots is one of the four majors in the Master's Programme in ICT Innovation. The Master's programme is organized by the School of Electrical Engineering and coordinated by the School of Science.

AUSIR Academic Coordinator: Quan Zhou, email: quan.zhou@aalto.fi

Planning Officer: Minna Parviainen (from 23.4.2025 onwards Riina Kontkanen, email: riina.kontkanen@aalto.fi)

Study Coordinator: Elsa Levo (elsa.levo@aalto.fi)

A1.1. Classes calendar

The academic year at Aalto University is divided into two terms: the autumn term begins annually on 1 August and ends on 31 December of that year. The spring term begins annually on 1 January and ends on 31 July of that year.

Academic year 2024–2025

Autumn term 2024

Teaching/evaluation period	Time	Week numbers
First evaluation period and orientation	26 Aug – 1 Sep 2024	35
Period I and evaluation week	2 Sep – 20 Oct 2024 no teaching or examinations 3 September after 12 o'clock (Opening ceremony)	36-42
Period II and evaluation week	21 Oct – 8 Dec 2024	43-49
Second evaluation period	9 Dec – 15 Dec 2024	50

Spring term 2025

Teaching/evaluation period	Time	Week numbers
Period III and evaluation week	6 Jan – 23 Feb 2025	2-8
Period IV and evaluation week	24 Feb – 13 Apr 2025	9-15
Period V: multimodal period in which diverse forms of teaching are implemented, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teaching for 6 weeks including intensive periods of evaluation of learning with diverse lengths Project course which starts with contact teaching and continues as summer project Summer schools 	14 Apr – 6 Jun 2025 no teaching or examinations 17 – 23 April 2025 (spring break)	16-23

A1.2. Enrolled students

Number of students: 18 (cohort 2024), out of which there are 12 males, 6 females, 5 EU students and 13 non-EU students.

One EU male student withdrew from the programme in September 2024 and did not arrive in Finland. **Subsequently, the number of active (on-track) students is 17.**

A1.3. Study plan

The Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots (AUSIR) - SPECTRO study programme is a combination of computer science and electrical engineering. During the programme, students gain new skills in both areas. In computer science, relevant skills include internet of things, machine learning, artificial intelligence and machine vision. In electrical engineering, relevant skills are automation, robotics, control, embedded systems and communications.

Entry year studies consist of Major studies 36 ECTS and I&E minor studies 24 ECTS with a minimum 60 ECTS. Full curriculum and learning outcomes of the major are available at the following link:

<https://www.aalto.fi/en/programmes/masters-programme-in-ict-innovation/curriculum-2024-2026#8-autonomous-systems-and-intelligent-robots>

A1.3.1. Student support services

ICT Innovation Master's programme student services employ two full-time staff members: a **Planning Officer** and a **Study Coordinator**, both of whom serve the needs of students and academic personnel within the School of Science's Learning Services unit and working partly for SPECTRO.

The Planning Officer's responsibilities encompass providing general oversight of the programme and its administration, compiling reports and statistics and managing the application and local admission processes. Planning Officer is also the primary contact for SPECTRO partner universities and is responsible for organizing introductory courses for new students as well as coordinating joint events and activities.

The Study Coordinator is tasked with offering general study guidance, facilitating enrolment and assisting with personal study plans. They manage the thesis and graduation processes, handle transcripts and issue other certificates and official documents.

In addition to programme-specific services, Aalto University offers a common service point for all students called **Starting Point**. This low-threshold service provides general guidance and assists all students in locating the appropriate support services.

A1.4. Student Progress

Number of credits completed, in average: 54,8 ECTS per student (per June 12, 2025).

Out of the 17 SPECTRO students 16 students have completed minimum 50 ECTS credits. Only one student is delayed, having completed 35 ECTS.

Summer School (4 ECTS) will be counted towards entry year studies and registered in August 2025 for all students.

A1.5. Organized events for the students

Student tutors

New SPECTRO students were appointed a tutor from a local student guild for the academic year 2024-2025. Tutors help with practical matters during the first days after arrival in Finland such as settling in, enrolment and getting to know the campus. Tutors may contact new students via email already during

the summer before the academic year starts. Tutors play a crucial role, particularly during the initial weeks of the autumn term.

Online info session 13 August

Before the orientation week, an online study planning session was held for new ICT Innovation Master's students on Zoom. SPECTRO students could pose major-specific questions in a break-out room.

Orientation week 26-30 August, 2024

Welcome sessions, 26 and 28 August

The welcome session for all ICT Innovation Master's students took place on Monday, August 26. Subsequently, the SPECTRO students' welcome event was held on Wednesday, August 28.

These events provided insights into studying and student life, courses, the study environment, university practices, and available services. Students also had the opportunity to meet fellow students, tutors, staff, and faculty.

Aalto Welcome Fair, 29 August

At the Aalto Welcome Fair, new students will have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the diverse services provided by Aalto University and its partners. At the exhibition booths, students can participate in activities, ask questions, and get to know people who can support them in their student life.

EIT labelled Master's programmes event, 30 August

EIT labelled Master's programme event gathered new SPECTRO students to learn and discuss innovation and entrepreneurship themes.

Aalto Day One, 3 September

Opening of a new academic year at Aalto University for all members and partners of the Aalto community.

Aalto Wellbeing Week, 30 September to 4 October

Aalto Wellbeing Week is an annual event for all members of Aalto community. Workshops, classes and offerings are available during the week to support general wellbeing of employees and students, including SPECTRO students at Aalto.

EIT Master Seasonal Get-together, 11 December

EIT Master Seasonal get-together was held at the end of autumn semester in an informal setting for SPECTRO students at Aalto together with other ICT Innovation Master's programme students.

A1.5.1. Workshops or Seminars offered

Intercultural communication & Learning Shock, October 11

Intercultural communication & Learning Shock event was organized for SPECTRO students together with other ICT Innovation Master's programme students and SECULO (Master's Programme in Security and Cloud Computing) students. The event focused on the theme of cultural adjustment in a new country and study environment, emphasizing how such transitions can affect students living far from home in unexpected ways. The event explored how cultural differences can shape the learning experience, influencing students' perceptions of their peers, their teachers, and the academic environment in which they study.

A1.5.2. Career Fair and job market activities

Most career fairs and job market activities at Aalto University are targeted to exit students searching for thesis positions; however, entry students are welcome to these events.

Aalto Thesis Day (2 October) is designated for companies and other organisations looking for international students to do Master's thesis in research or development projects. The events, lectures and meet-ups were open for SPECTRO entry students as well.

Aalto Career Design Lab offers free services such as support in career design and job search, career fairs and events, courses and trainings, career coaching and mentoring as well as connections to Finnish Employers and Aalto Alumni. All these services are available for SPECTRO students at Aalto.

Mentors

Mentors are assigned exclusively to exit students. Mentors provide support in finding master's thesis positions and internships, as well as assisting with integration into Finnish working culture. Mentors also facilitate interaction and help create a peer support environment for the students. Mentors for SPECTRO exit students are already assigned for the academic year 2025-2026.

A1.6. Feedback from students

AllWell? Student Survey

Allwell? Student Survey is conducted in the spring for all Aalto University's 2nd-year bachelor's students and 1st-year master's students. The survey provides students with an opportunity to share their experiences related to teaching and counselling, and how they perceive the Aalto learning environment. Additionally, students assess their own resources and study skills.

Summary of survey results (SPECTRO AUSIR students)

There were 8 respondents from the Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots major (44,4% response rate).

Use of time per week (average hours): Use of time for studies: 50,13 h. Use of time for paid work: 10,63 h.

Section 1: Teaching and guidance:

Students generally find the programme structure clear, and the teaching well aligned with learning goals. Engagement with course content is high, and most report a good understanding of what is expected of them. Feedback and workload receive more varied responses, with some noting occasional imbalance or limited feedback. While guidance services are widely available, a few students mention the need for more individualized support.

Section 2: Personal resources:

Most respondents report strong personal resources, particularly in concentration, executive function, wellbeing, and clarity regarding their academic and career direction. A few indicate that life circumstances or limited social connection may affect their study experience. Overall, the results reflect a solid foundation for study engagement, with some variation in individual situations.

Section 3: Study skills:

Most students report strong self-efficacy, prior knowledge, and use of deep learning strategies. Organizational skills are generally well developed, with students showing systematic approaches to planning their studies. Some respondents, however, experience self-critical thoughts and test-related anxiety, and a few report difficulties in understanding or structuring complex material. These responses suggest that while core study skills are solid for most, individual variation exists, especially in emotional aspects of learning.

Section 4: Risk of study-related burnout:

< Palaa raporttiin

RISK OF STUDY-RELATED BURNOUT

Some of the eight respondents report feelings of stress, inadequacy, and reduced motivation, with study-related concerns occasionally affecting their recovery and free time. The reported weekly workload, on average over 50 hours for studies and an additional 10 hours of paid work, may contribute to these experiences. While most students remain motivated and engaged, these findings highlight the impact of sustained academic pressure. Given the small sample size and possibly self-selecting bias, the results should be interpreted with caution. Nonetheless, they point to the importance of maintaining a manageable workload and ensuring that students are aware of available support when needed.

A1.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

Joint degree programmes at Aalto University

The webpage for Joint degree programmes provides information on available programmes, eligibility criteria, application procedures, benefits of joint degrees, and contact details for admissions inquiries. Potential applicants can find details on required documents and application deadlines to assist in the application process:

<https://www.aalto.fi/en/admission-services/international-joint-degree-programmes>

Joint degree programmes are also marketed locally to Aalto exchange students, sometimes in connection with courses by professors and through exchange student newsletters.

International student marketing and recruitment at Aalto

International student marketing and recruitment at Aalto is organized either Aalto-wide, school-level or programme level. These activities are complementary and support each other. Aalto’s recruitment target markets and strategically selected countries for 2025 were China, India, Indonesia, Turkey and Vietnam (non-EU) and Germany, Italy, Poland, Estonia and Latvia (EU/EEA). Marketing and

recruitment actions include owned channels, tactical digital marketing, local recruitment activities and education agents.

Study Fairs and events in 2024

Aalto's student marketing specialists attended several international study fairs in 2024, aiming to connect with potential SPECTRO applicants as part of a wider outreach campaign. It should be noted that not all events necessarily featured SPECTRO-specific marketing materials.

-India: QS Higher Education Master's Fairs in Delhi, Mumbai and Hyderabad, April 2024; in Pune, Mumbai, Hyderabad, Chennai and Bangalore, December 2024

-Indonesia: EHEF European Higher Education Fair, Jakarta and Yogyakarta, October-November 2024

-Turkey: A2 International Education Fair in Istanbul, October 2024

-Vietnam: Study in Europe events in Ho Chi Minh and Hanoi, October and November 2024

-Romania: IUF Fair in Bucharest, October 2024

Aalto Double Degree Day

The annual Aalto Double Degree Day was held on Wednesday, November 20, 2024. The event is organized by the Aalto Joint Master Group and designed for students interested to earning Master's degrees concurrently and studying in two different countries. Participants had the opportunity to meet staff, students and mentors from all the joint degree programs Aalto offers. They could hear presentations, ask questions about the programmes, explore career opportunities, learn from student experiences, and receive information on how to apply.

During the event, SPECTRO marketing materials were made available and promoted alongside other major programs in ICT Innovation. Aalto Double Degree Day 20.11.24 | Aalto University

A1.8. Lesson learned

The first year of SPECTRO implementation at Aalto University has highlighted several strengths in both programme structure and student support. Despite staff transitions and resource challenges within the student services unit, the programme maintained continuity through agile reallocation of tasks. Active monitoring practices, such as periodic progress checks, reminder emails, and personal meetings, proved valuable in supporting students' academic progression. Feedback from students has generally been appreciative, reflecting satisfaction with both the academic structure and the accessibility of guidance.

Regular coordination between the academic and administrative sides of the programme helped ensure clarity and responsiveness. These internal communication practices created a solid foundation for managing student needs and maintaining academic quality.

Student feedback from the AllWell? survey suggests that most students feel confident in their academic abilities and perceive the programme structure as clear and coherent. However, some students indicated challenges related to stress, life circumstances, or limited awareness of available support services. This suggests that one area of improvement lies not in creating new support mechanisms, but in informing students more proactively, for example, by highlighting existing wellbeing and guidance services more clearly during orientation events and early-semester touchpoints. Students may also benefit from reminders that it is normal to seek help and that support is not only available but encouraged.

In terms of external engagement, dissemination of the SPECTRO programme has so far been modest. While student recruitment has been strong, the lack of formal dissemination activities, such as conference presentations, outreach to partner institutions, or public visibility in relevant networks, represents a missed opportunity to share best practices and raise the profile of the programme. This is a point for improvement in Year 2: identifying low-threshold opportunities for dissemination, such as contributing to academic events, updating public materials, or coordinating with existing Aalto communications channels.

Looking ahead, improvements will focus on maintaining the successful academic foundation, enhancing clarity of support services, and increasing programme visibility. These steps can be achieved without significant resource demands, while still reinforcing student experience and institutional alignment with the objectives of the SPECTRO project.

A2. Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)

Report of activities

BME participates both in the entry and exit year of the MSC programme in AUSIR. The coordination of BME educational activities happens at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Informatics as most of the courses delivered to the AUSIR students are hosted by this faculty. All courses are in English and accredited by the faculty and registered in the university's study management systems. The course content of AUSIR programme at BME is developed as part of the SPECTRO project, hence it complies with the project's workplan.

During the study periods at BME, AUSIR students are subject to obligations defined in the Code of Studies of the university with a few exceptions related to the Thesis Work requirements as the Thesis Work is completed in the AUSIR programme during a single semester whereas it is expected to be completed at BME during two semesters.

A2.1. Classes calendar

Let us focus on the organization of the entry year since no exit year curriculum was delivered during the academic year 2024/2025. At BME, the entry year follows the traditional two-semesters structure. Each semester is organized as follows:

The registration period of the 2024 Fall (respectively 2025 Spring) semester started on August 26, 2024 (respectively February 3, 2025) and the exam period ended on January 24, 2025 (respectively June 30, 2025). The detailed academic calendar is published on-line with holidays and other university events.

AUSIR students were assisted in course enrolment during the Registration & orientation week, they follow the classes during the next 14 weeks according to a weekly schedule. One week of resits and repeats is provided for students who need or wish to improve their results obtained during the period of classes and the semester is concluded by an exam period where comprehensive exams are programmed for some of the courses.

The entire study workflow (including the course enrolment, results, registration for exams, finances, etc.) is managed using an electronic study management system called Neptun which has an English language interface.

The weekly schedule of classes of the AUSIR students for the 2025 fall semester is shown below (the lists of courses are provided in the Study plan section).

Hour	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday		Thursday	Friday
08:15-09 ¹	AutRob # I-B307	CtrlLab1 tentative no session during 1 st week	AI-Ctrl + I-B310		Emb-AI #	Emb-AI
09:15-10						
10:15-11	AI-Ctrl I-B310					
11:15-12						
12:15-13			AutROB Q-BF08			
13:15-14						
14:15-15	Stochastics I-B145	DL I-B146	DL+ I-B147		Stochastics I-B145	
15:15-16						

The weekly schedule of classes of the AUSIR students for the 2025 spring semester is shown below.

Hour	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
08:15-09 ¹	Linear Algebra E407	Econ. Analysis of Technology QA404			Engineering management QBF09
09:15-10					
10:15-11	Machine Learning IE224			Linear Algebra IB138	
11:15-12					
12:15-13	Tech. comm. E306	V2X for UAVs IB111		V2X for UAVs t.b.d.	
13:15-14					
14:15-15			Machine learning IL306	Computer Vision systems + IB410	
15:15-16					Embedded System Security t.b.d.
16:15-17			Project Management QB104		
17:15-18					

On both tables, green color classes are lectures; light blue color classes are laboratory sessions and cantaloupe color classes are classroom practice sessions. The presence of students is required during classroom and laboratory sessions (in accordance with the Code of Studies of BME.) Let us remark that the Project laboratory course has no scheduled class since students are expected to meet weekly with their topic supervisors during a mutually agreed time slot.

A2.2. Enrolled students

In the 2024/2025 academic year, BME had **three** entry year (male) students attending the AUSIR track. Two students are EU citizens. The BSc degree of the third student (from India) was “weaker” (attended earlier a lower number of related courses) in computer engineering than the background of most other students on taking the courses of the study plan therefore this student received some advice for additional readings and exercises to catch up. His projects for the different courses were adapted to his background especially during the first semester.

All three enrolled students completed successfully the entry year. It was nice to observe a positive group dynamic in this team of three international students as they were successfully teamed up for some projects during the entry year. Moreover, they came up with an interesting business idea related to a AI-based service to check companies compliance with GDPR rules.

A2.3. Study plan

The study plans of the AUSIR entry year at the BME comply with the SPECTRO project requirements. It includes mandatory courses and elective components. Some elective components are included into the study plans of students to compensate for unfavorably biased background due to earlier studies. Study plans are personally presented to all AUSIR students during the registration week of the entry year so they get information about the courses’ content, pre-requisites, expected level of difficulties and the credit requirements. Students are also explained the options they may have in terms of elective courses. (The details of course syllabi are explained by the lecturers in charge during the first class.)

The following table shows the study plan of AUSIR students during the 2024 fall semester. The study plan allows 32 credits to collect. (Let us note that the abbreviations in the table are used in the weekly schedules provided earlier.)

Code (Neptun)	Title	Credits	Weekly contact hours ²	Req.
BMEVIIIIMA12	Autonomous robots and vehicles (AutRob)	4	2/1/0	exam
BMEVIIIIMB06	Artificial Intelligence Based Control (AI-Ctrl)	5	2/1/0	exam
BMEVIMIMA22	Embedded Artificial Intelligence (Emb-AI)	5	2/1/0	exam
BMEVITMMA19	Deep Learning (DL)	5	2/1/0	exam
BMEGT20M402	Innovation and entrepreneurship basics (I&E Basics)	5	4/0/0	ms.m. ³
BMEGT20M403	Business development laboratory I. (I&E Lab)	4	0/3/0	ms.m.
BMEVIIIIMA11	Control eng. and image processing lab. 1 (CtrlLab1)	4	0/0/3	ms.m.
BMETE90MX80	Stochastics	5	4/0/0	exam

Legend

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The following table shows the study plan of AUSIR students during the 2025 spring semester. The study plan allows 30 credits to collect. The last three listed courses were additional elective courses for students (if they are interested).

Code (Neptun)	Title	Credits	Weekly contact hours ²	Req.	
BMEVIMIMA27	Machine Learning	5	2/1/0	exam	
BMEVIHIMB12	Embedded System Security	4	2/1/0	exam	
BMEVIHIAV37 ³	V2X Communication Technologies of Autonomous Vehicles (V2X for UAVs)	4	3/1/0	exam	
BMEVIIIIMA07 ³	Computer Vision Systems	4	2/1/0	exam	
BMEVIIIIML12	Project laboratory 1 ⁴	5	0/0/3	ms.m. ⁵	
BMETE90MX78	Linear Algebra (advanced)	5	4/0/0	exam	
BMEGT20M404	EIT Business development practice II	3	0/2/0	ms.m.	
BMEVITMMB03	Engineering management	4	4/0/0	exam	
BMEGT30MS07	Economic Analysis of Technology	2	0/2/0	exam	
BMEVIHIAV51	Technical Communication in Industry and Academia	2	2/0/0	ms.m	
BMEGT20M420	Project Management	2	0/2/0	ms.m.	
Total		18	5	7	2/3

A2.4. Student Progress

All three AUSIR students completed 62 ECTS during the entry year with better grades than the average (of students taking the courses in the study plans). This means that they have the full potential to successfully complete the MSC degree program. Student progress were steady, all three students remained motivated and efficient during the entire entry year.

Concerning the three suggested additional and elective courses during the second semester of the entry year, students selected one course and visited classes, but later dropped them without getting credits.

A2.5. Organized events for the students

The AUSIR students at BME were invited to and participated in several events organized by BME and by partners, especially the Eötvös Lóránd Science University (ELTE) whose campus is located close to BME and they also have AUSIR students. Joint events provided excellent opportunities for the students to build their professional and personal networks, and to improve their professional skillset through acquiring new, up-to-date knowledge.

Several meetings were organized with BME AUSIR students where they were given information about the studies and they reported the status of their courses.

September 2–4 Welcome Week for AUSIR students with other international MSc students (welcome, introduction, team building, enrolment, registration, university requirements, campus tour, Budapest Node introduction, opening ceremony, information market, scavenger hunt, city tour, karaoke night)

October 3–4 EIT Digital Master School Kick-Off in Riga

A2.5.1. Workshops or Seminars offered

Students did present their Project laboratory results (2025 spring semester) during the mini workshop. No other workshop or seminar is scheduled during the entry year.

A2.5.2. Career Fair and job market activities

On April 10, 2025, Eötvös Loránd University organized a Career Day at the Faculty of Informatics. The 700 registered students could visit 42 company stands, find career opportunities, meet company ambassadors, receive advice on creating a successful CV and take CV photos, as well as attend mock interviews. (<https://allasborze.elte.hu/elte-karriernap-career-day/>)

The Faculty of Informatics has opened a robot lab in collaboration with European Knowledge Center, a Hungarian company specializing in autonomous systems and artificial intelligence. SPECTRO students were invited to the official opening ceremony where they could meet company representatives and discuss positions and potential job openings.

In addition, SPECTRO students were also invited to participate in a workshop series organized for the Intelligent Field Robotic Systems (IFRoS) students. Here, they could attend a series of lectures given by university research labs and companies such as GIM Robotics, Euroknows, and HUN-REN SZTAKI.

In collaboration with Bosch, the Faculty of Informatics organized the first Intelligent Robotics Fair Conference and Expo between June 23-25, 2025. SPECTRO students were invited to submit papers,

attend the conferences and meet company ambassadors at the expo. (https://introb-fair.inf.elte.hu/?fbclid=IwY2xjawLlsmZleHRuA2FibQIxMABicmlkETFuT1RCMG93Q0JtRGFtMmh6AR6VxiZ2cL6_SJFWuupFthiKT4uShA_Wf5Bqqgdhx0355eLSs9d_CYA9N6ubXw_aem_xSWrTzmrnkLM DJEINcWqTQ)

A2.6. Feedback from students

Three types of feedback were collected from AUSIR students.

All students are expected to provide feedback for each attended course using BME's stud management system on a voluntary bases. All results are anonymized. Since most of the courses are attended by non-AUSIR international students as well, the results are mixed. Since the space is limited, let us provide some results related to some courses:

Artificial Intelligence based control (2024 fall, BMEVIIMB06), Question: overall evaluation of the lecture (1 – absolutely inappropriate; 6 – fully appropriate) 4 answers were provided including 3 AUSIR students

Colors: red – avg of answers; yellow – avg at the department; green – avg at the faculty

Autonomos robots and vehicles (2024 fall, BMEVIIMA12), Question: evaluate the lecturer's ways of teaching (methodology, pedagogy); 1 – absolutely inappropriate; 6 – excellent in all aspects) 18 answers were provided including 3 AUSIR students

Colors: red – avg of answers; yellow – avg at the department; green – avg at the faculty

Computer vision systems (2025 spring, BMEVIIIIMA07), Question: overall evaluation of the lecture (1 – absolutely inappropriate; 6 – fully appropriate) 10 answers were provided including 3 AUSIR students

Colors: red – avg of answers; yellow – avg at the department; green – avg at the faculty

Considering also the other courses where sufficient answer were provided, one may conclude that the evaluation results provided for courses attended by AUSIR students showed results superior to departmental and faculty averages.

1. AUSIR students were also asked to fill in SPECTRO project specific forms, the results are collected by the appropriate WP lead.
2. Regular meetings with AUSIR students were also sources of informal feedbacks, mainly about the difficulty level of modules of some courses. If this were necessary, the AUSIR coordinator discussed the catch-up advices with the lecturer of the course in question.

A2.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

February 25, 2025: Pizza session for potential applicants, jointly organized by ELTE Special information session for bachelor students interested in master programmes with entrepreneurship education. Number of participants: 8

The AUSIR track opportunity was published using multiple channels to BME BSC students. These channels include facebook, newsletters.

Dissemination activities included:

Continuous update of the description of SPECTRO and the AUSIR programme on the website of the Faculty.

Presentation of the programme (usually using slides) to industrial and international partners during their visits and if coordinator visits such partners.

A2.8. Lesson learned

The AUSIR programme was created by combining already existing and newly created courses in compliance with the SPECTRO project requirements. Based on student feedback, the quality of the courses are excellent.

Students require more regular informal meetings to discuss the status of the program. These meeting allows the coordinator to evaluate also the general well-being of the students in terms of their integration into a new cultural and study environment.

More events are expected by the students related to the industry in autonomous systems and robotics. Since such partners are available the number of such events will be increased.

A3. Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE)

Report of activities

A3.1. Classes calendar

At Eötvös Loránd University, the academic year consists of a fall semester and a spring semester. In the fall semester, students are required to take 28 ECTS credits of compulsory courses, while in the spring semester, they must take 32 ECTS credits of compulsory courses. In the first year of study, students are required to complete a total of 60 ECTS credits of compulsory courses at ELTE, listed in 2.3.

The study period of the fall semester began on September 9 and ended on December 13, with a fall break between October 28 – November 1. The exam period began on December 16 and ended on February 1, with no exams on December 24–26 and January 1.

The study period of the spring semester began on February 10 and ended on May 16, with a spring break between April 16–22. The exam period began on May 19 and ended on July 4.

A3.2. Enrolled students

In the 2024/2025 academic year, ELTE had one entry year female student attending the AUSIR track; she is from the EU.

A3.3. Study plan

The courses and ECTS in the 2024/2025 fall semester were as follows:

Technical courses:

3D Computer Vision L+Pr. 6

Introduction to Vehicles and Sensors 4

Principles of artificial intelligence 6

Preparation course for master studies and developing learning skills Pr. 2

I&E Module:

I&E Basics 6

Business Development Lab I.4

The courses and ECTS in the 2024/2025 spring semester were as follows:

Technical courses:

Deep Reinforcement Learning L+Pr. 6

Intelligent Mobile Robots 6

Image and Video Processing L.+Pr. 6

I&E Module:

Business Development Lab II. 4

Innosocial aspects of entrepreneurship 6

Thematic Summer Schools with I&E project 4

A3.4. Student Progress

As of mid-July, our student has completed 55 ECTS of compulsory and elective courses. This does not include the 4 ECTS of “Thematic Summer Schools with I&E project,” the grade for which will be entered in September. She has failed to complete one compulsory course which she will retake remotely during her exit year to complete her mandatory entry courses. Therefore, she is still on track for graduation.

In addition to the mandatory courses, our student has also taken an elective course relevant to her studies, and supported one of her lecturers as a teaching assistant.

A3.5. Organized events for the students

The SPECTRO students at ELTE were invited to and participated in several events organized by Eötvös Loránd University and by partner institutes. These events provided excellent opportunities for the students to build their professional and personal networks, and to improve their professional skillset through acquiring new, up-to-date knowledge.

September 2–4 Welcome Week for AUSIR students with other international MSc students (welcome, introduction, team building, enrolment, registration, university requirements, campus tour, Budapest Node introduction, opening ceremony, information market, scavenger hunt, city tour, karaoke night)

October 3–4 EIT Digital Master School Kick-Off in Riga

May 17 Eurovision Song Contest watch party

A3.5.1. Workshops or Seminars offered

The workshops and seminars organized in the 2024/2025 academic year were not specifically for SPECTRO students, instead, they were targeting all computer science autonomous systems students studying at an MSc level at ELTE.

SPECTRO students were invited to participate in a workshop series organized for the Intelligent Field Robotic Systems (IFRoS) students (December 5-6, 2024). Here, they could attend a series of lectures given by university research labs and companies such as GIM Robotics, European Knowledge Center, and HUN-REN SZTAKI.

In the spring semester (March 26, 2025), an employee at the European Knowledge Center robot lab taught a seminar on sensors to a group of students, including our SPECTRO AUSIR student. The employee was an intern from the Intelligent Field Robotic Systems (IFRoS) programme which underscores not only the university's industry connections but also the close proximity in the programmes taught by the university, uniting students with similar interests and study plans.

A3.5.2. Career Fair and job market activities

On April 10, 2025, Eötvös Loránd University organized a Career Day at the Faculty of Informatics. The 700 registered students could visit 42 company stands, find career opportunities, meet company ambassadors, receive advice on creating a successful CV and take CV photos, as well as attend mock interviews. (<https://allasborze.elte.hu/elte-karriernap-career-day/>)

The Faculty of Informatics has opened a robot lab in collaboration with European Knowledge Center, a Hungarian company specializing in autonomous systems and artificial intelligence. SPECTRO students were invited to the official opening ceremony where they could meet company representatives and discuss positions and potential job openings.

In addition, SPECTRO students were also invited to participate in a workshop series organized for the Intelligent Field Robotic Systems (IFRoS) students. Here, they could attend a series of lectures given by university research labs and companies such as GIM Robotics, Euroknows, and HUN-REN SZTAKI.

In collaboration with Bosch, the Faculty of Informatics organized the first Intelligent Robotics Fair Conference and Expo between June 23-25, 2025. SPECTRO students were invited to submit papers, attend the conferences and meet company ambassadors at the expo. (https://introb-fair.inf.elte.hu/?fbclid=IwY2xjawLlsmZleHRuA2FibQlxMABicmlkETFuT1RCMG93Q0JtRGFtMmh6AR6VxiZ2cL6_SJFW_uupFthiKT4uShA_Wf5Bqqgdhx0355eLSs9d_CYA9N6ubXw_aem_xSWrTzmrnkLMDJEINcWqTQ)

A3.6. Feedback from students

As we only had one AUSIR student in this academic year, we were unable to collect formal feedback in compliance with GDPR. However, both the programme lead and the student coordinator discussed the student's experience informally. She was satisfied with the courses and the SPECTRO programme in general, with the study plan and the elective courses offered by the university. In addition, she enjoyed getting to know autonomous systems students from the non-SPECTRO university programme whom she attended classes with. Regarding the failed course, she is prepared to take on a heavier workload in the exit year to make up for the missing ECTS.

A3.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

November 28, 2024: ELTE Faculty of Informatics Open Day for high school students, link: <https://www.inf.elte.hu/nyiltnap2024ik> Despite the event targeting students yet to begin their BSc studies, a number of high schoolers are quite conscious of their preferred study plan so they had numerous questions at the EIT Digital/SPECTRO stand. We also believe it is beneficial to inform them of MSc opportunities this early on so they can plan their BSc studies accordingly. In addition, ELTE BSc students assisting with the event also approached the student coordinator to ask questions about the opportunities provided by the double degree programme. Number of participants: 900.

January 17, 2025: ELTE Faculty of Informatics Open Day for high school students, link: <https://www.inf.elte.hu/nyiltnap2024ik> Similarly to the November event, numerous high schoolers and BSc students approached the student coordinator to ask questions about the opportunities provided by the double degree programme. Number of participants: 650.

February 25, 2025: Pizza session for potential applicants, Special information session for bachelor students interested in master programmes with entrepreneurship education. Number of participants: 8

April 2, 2025: Facebook post for recruiting students to the SPECTRO programme. Link: <https://www.facebook.com/ELTEIKinternational/posts/pfbid0UGde8qVgaVyTjoT4p2Wn69j3wspuvA9gc4Ym71MT6ctEuVc76t1sT1vquUEeppAl>

LinkedIn post about SPECTRO, posted by ELTE, shared by Zoltán Istenes (AUSIR programme lead):
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/zoltanistenes_spectro-university-elte-activity-7313988987432386561-OCFD?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAFD2DzgB0Z07_h52hV_8QCrJQoUk6Y4gXVs

May 7, 2025: Idea Competition and EIT Digital, SPECTRO, EMAI recruitment event targeting ELTE BSc students with an interest in entrepreneurship. Number of participants: 60

Zoltán Istenes, AUSIR programme lead at ELTE, discussed the importance of the AUSIR programme in a LinkedIn post about his current students.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/zoltanistenes_spectro-ai-artificialintelligence-activity-7296226109543575553-Kfmu?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAFD2DzgB0Z07_h52hV_8QCrJQoUk6Y4gXVs

The previously mentioned official opening of the European Knowledge Center robot lab at the Faculty of Informatics served as a dissemination activity as well since we plan to further strengthen the industry collaborations with the programme. This includes organizing lab visits and seminars, offering internship projects to exit year SPECTRO students in the upcoming academic years, etc. LinkedIn post: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/zoltanistenes_robotics-ai-innovation-activity-7306392029721169920-nGZQ?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAFD2DzgB0Z07_h52hV_8QCrJQoUk6Y4gXVs)

LinkedIn post about Zoltán Istenes's attendance at the Syros Summer School.
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/zoltanistenes_eitdigital-spectro-summer-school-activity-7343204014072782851-pzCS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAFD2DzgB0Z07_h52hV_8QCrJQoUk6Y4gXVs

A3.8. Lesson learned

The AUSIR programme at ELTE was created by combining already existing courses and newly created courses. It was an interesting challenge to form new subjects that complemented the pre-existing ones in order to provide a well-rounded foundational year for SPECTRO students. We believe that we succeeded in constructing a study plan that adequately prepares our entry year students for their second year abroad. Since some of our courses were taught for the first time this year, we are aware that they need to be refined and updated in the upcoming years to ensure they fit student expectations

and their master's journey. We are enthusiastic to continue improving our mandatory courses, and are excited to see what the next year brings with our first exit year SPECTRO students.

Locally, we worked together with Faculty staff (Vice Dean for Education, lecturers from other Institutes) to create the best possible study plan and to ensure we comply with university and national regulations. We also employ a student advisor who specifically aids EIT Digital and SPECTRO students to help them navigate local and programme requirements.

As ELTE only had one AUSIR student in the 2024/2025 academic year, she had to form connections with students from other, similar programmes offered by the university (Computer Science - Autonomous Systems specialization, Intelligent Field Robotic Systems [IFRoS]). We made sure she felt included in student activities and the university environment. Our Co-Location Centre is meant to be a shared space where students from different international MSc programmes can connect and study together, work on shared projects and learn from each other.

We continued to build and strengthen industry connections this year to ensure we have more and more projects and opportunities to offer our students (European Knowledge Center, GIM Robotics, etc). We plan to reach out to even more companies in the future, and include site visits to Bosch and ZalaZone, an automotive test track in the Hungarian countryside.

We are aware that our student numbers could be higher and we are actively working on increasing our recruitment efforts. We have been organizing events to connect with local BSc students, but we have not had the desired results yet. We will continue reaching out to this target demographic.

A4. EURECOM

Report of activities

A4.1. Classes calendar

At EURECOM the academic year is organized in two semesters (Fall and Spring). In 2025/2026 the calendar for Master students will follow this structure:

Welcome for International students – French Intensive classes (FLE): 1st September 2025

First semester classes: 16th September 2025 – 21st January 2026

Exam period: 22nd January 2026 – 06th February 2026

Second semester classes: 09th February 2026 – 9th June 2026

Exam period: 10th June 2026 – 26th June 2026

A4.2. Enrolled students

As we are an exit institution, we did not have any students in the academic year 2024/2025. However, we will receive the following 7 students in 2025/2026: 7 students: 7 males (6 non-EU and 1 EU).

A4.3. Study plan

The courses and ECTS in 2025/2026 for the Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots (AUSIR) are organized as follows:

Data Processing and Architecture		Unit ECTS: 5.00
		Min sum of Weight:
CompArch	Computer architecture	Weight: 1.00

I	MobMod	Mobility Modeling	Weight: 0.50
I	WebSem	Semantic Web and Information Extraction Technologies	Weight: 0.50
Innovation & entrepreneurship EIT			Unit ECTS: 6.00 Min sum of Weight:
G	I&E	Innovation and entrepreneurship EIT (external course)	Weight: 1.00
Software and Systems			Unit ECTS: 10.00 Min sum of Weight:
I	EmSim	Emulation and simulation methodologies	Weight: 0.25
I	MALIS	Machine Learning and Intelligent System	Weight: 0.50
I	MobSys	Mobile communication systems	Weight: 0.50
I	QUANTIS	Quantum Information Science	Weight: 0.25
I	SoftDev	Software development methodologies	Weight: 0.25
I	Stand	Standardization activities	Weight: 0.25
I	UMLEmb	Designing embedded systems with UML	Weight: 0.25

Language	French or another foreign language for French speakers	1
Semester project (including research methodology)		8

A4.4. Student Progress

As previously stated, EURECOM being an exit institution within this EIT Master Program, we did not have any student during the academic year 2024/2025. We will closely follow the 7 students expected to arrive next September for completing their year at our institution. They will need to complete their entire program of 60 ECTS (including the semester project).

A4.5. Organized events for the students

EURECOM shares the same campus with Université Côte d'Azur, so it contributed to some activities for students. Moreover, a list of activities carried out for master students at EURECOM is reported, which gives a good account of what will be delivered during the next fall for SPECTRO students.

September 28, 2024: EIT Digital Welcome meeting: Lunch organized in collaboration with Université Côte d'Azur to welcome students who joined the EIT Master program in Campus SophiaTech in 2024 together with staff involved in the project.

September 1, 2024: EURECOM organizes the Welcome event for all international students which opens a 3-week program of French intensive classes. This program, which is offered for free to international students, includes guided visits to the surroundings and cultural adjustment lessons to smooth integration.

Mid-September 2024: 2 to 3 days of administrative appointments are organized by the school to help students through their procedures of life in France (visa, housing, bank account opening...) and at the school (IT presentations, student life at EURECOM, etc).

Integration Weekend – End of September 2024: All newcomers are invited to participate in the integration weekend, organized by the Student Association in collaboration with EURECOM. This event is not mandatory but it is encouraged as a way to get involved in Student life at the School.

Career Fairs: As noted below, students are invited to join the two student fairs organized by EURECOM each year.

A4.5.1. Workshops or Seminars offered

In collaboration with UCA, we organize some EIT Digital Entrepreneurs Lunches through the Fall term to connect students with entrepreneurial interests, provide inspiration, and build networks in a casual, supportive environment.

A4.5.2. Career Fair and job market activities

In order to help the students to find a master's thesis based on an internship, EURECOM organizes two meetings per year.

The students are invited to one of them depending on their thesis/internship period:

- In October for a departure in March,
- In March for a departure in July,

The October meeting has been organized onsite. During this meeting, there is a short presentation on EURECOM's database (called the SIFI internship database) and how to apply for thesis/internship offers on SIFI.

The SIFI thesis/internship database is regularly updated for each thesis/internship period and each time we receive a new offer from a company. There are around 150 offers on SIFI every year. In addition, EURECOM's faculty is using its network to provide internship possibilities personalized to students who have a clear project idea.

A job/internship fair has been organized with 15 to 20 tech companies in October.

A4.6. Feedback from students

As we did not have any student participating in this program, we cannot provide their feedback for now. We expect to send a survey by the end of the academic year to all SPECTRO students to evaluate their satisfaction and suggest adjustments accordingly.

A4.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

EURECOM set up a web page dedicated to AUSIR programme within its teaching portal:

<https://www.eurecom.fr/en/teaching/european-double-degree-masters/master-autonomous-systems-and-intelligent-robots>

The page contains the logo of the EIT Digital Master School Programme, a brief introduction to EIT Digital, an overview of the core courses of the programme, the list of the partner Universities (and the links to their websites). It also includes the name of the specialization offered by each partner in the second year, as well as links to the EIT Digital MS website.

A special slide on EIT Digital master inserted in all the corporate presentations of EURECOM.

EURECOM advertised locally and internationally the AUSIR master

We continued in 2024/2025 to organize various webinars:

- In France: IMT Lille, Mines Albi, ENSSAT, ENSSEIHT, Mines St Etienne, Telecom St Etienne, ECE, ECAM
- In Tunisia: Esprit and Supcom
- In EU: Polito (Italy), TU Wien (Austria), NTNU (Norway), CTU (Czech Republic), Chalmers (Sweden), ULiège (Belgium)

We also participated in International student recruiting fairs via Campus France: Mexico, South Korea, India, China in which we used special promotion material to encourage students to join the EIT MS through our school.

Web Marketing:

EURECOM published updated presentation of the AUSIR programme on one portal of reference:

On Campus France TIE, the French national directory of academic programs taught in English:
<https://taughtie.campusfrance.org/tiesearch/#/program/1917>

Additionally, EURECOM also did several social media posts to promote the EIT Digital programs (LinkedIn, Instagram).

Selection and admission of candidates

We assessed all the candidates that chose EURECOM as Exit University for intake 2024.

Application reviews were assigned between the program coordinator and the administrative manager. Any questionable candidates were discussed as a team.

A4.8. Lesson learned

EURECOM did not encounter any specific difficulties in preparing for welcoming SPECTRO AUSIR and CSES students from this Fall 2025 for the exit year of the first cohort. We have continued to market the programmes widely, in Europe through the EURECOM academic members located in France, Sweden, Finland, Norway, Belgium, Germany, Austria, Italy and Czech Republic, and via very large recruitment fairs under the patronage of Campus France in Mexico, India and China.

A5. KTH

Report of activities

A5.1. Classes calendar

Education is organized in 4 periods/quarters.

Academic year 2024 - 25

Autumn semester dates: 26 august 2024 - 13 January 2025

Study period 1, 26 August - 11 October

Own work: 14–16 October 2024

Exam period 1: 17–18 October and 21–25 October 2024

Study period 2, 28 October - 13 December

Own work / re-exams: 16 December–19 December

Own work: 20 December 2024–3 January 2025

Exam period 2: 7–11 January 2025 and 13 January 2025

National Holiday: 25–26 December 2024, 1 January 2025 and 6 January 2025

Spring semester dates: 14 January 2025 - 2 June 2025

Study period 3, 14 January - 3 March

Own work: 4–6 March 2025

Exam period 3: 7–8 March and 10–14 March 2025

Study period 4, 17 March - 20 May

Own work / re-exams: 22–25 April 2025

Own work: 2 May 2025 and 21–23 May 2025

Exam period 4: 26 May–28 May and 30 May–31 May and 2 June 2025

National Holiday: 18 April, 21 April 2025, 1 May and 29 May 2025

Re-exam period: 3 June–5 June 2025

A5.2. Enrolled students

There were enrolled 20 students for the Entry year of the program at KTH. Among them 5 are EU nationals and 15 non-EU nationals. Also 3 of the admitted students are females and 17 are males.

A5.3. Study plan

The set of courses for Entry students in 2024/25 is completely compliant with the list of courses presented in the Annex in 2.1.

ENTRY YEAR		60 ECTS	
FIRST SEMESTER			36 ECTS
Compulsory courses			30 ECTS
Introduction to Robotics		7.5	
Machine learning		7.5	
Research Methodology and Scientific Writing		7.5	
Distributed AI and Intelligent Agents		7.5	
Electives courses (form the list below)			0 ECTS
I&E			6 ECTS
Entrepreneurship for Engineers		6	
SECOND SEMESTER			24 ECTS
Compulsory courses			0 ECTS
Elective courses (from the list of elective courses below, can also be taken in the first semester)			7.5 ECTS
I&E			9 ECTS
Business Development Lab of Entrepreneurship Engineers		9	
One I&E Conditionally Compulsory Course (from the list below)			7.5 ECTS
Technology-based Entrepreneurship		7.5	
Internet Marketing		7.5	

e-Business Strategies		7.5	
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List of Recommended Electives courses	Semester		
Analysis and Search of Visual Data	1	7.5	
Cyber-Physical Networking	1	7.5	
Embedded Systems	1	7.5	
Image Analysis and Computer Vision	1	7.5	
Artificial Intelligence	1	6.0	
Automatic Control, General Course	1	6.0	
Stochastic Simulation	1	7.5	
Hybrid and Embedded Control Systems	2	7.5	
Speech and Audio Processing	2	7.5	
Deep Learning in Data Science	2	7.5	
Control Theory and Practice, Advanced Course	2	7.5	
Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning	2	7.5	

All active students took all compulsory and I&E courses.

Among the elective courses:

13 students took the Deep Learning in Data Science course

2 students took the Project course in Robotics and Autonomous Systems course

1 student took the Hybrid and Embedded Control Systems course

1 student took the Computer Aided Manufacturing course

1 student took the Interactive Programming and the Dynamic Web course

A5.4. Student Progress

The recent data about students' progress is as follows:

11 students have 60 ECTS

1 student has 59 ECTS

1 student has 58,5 ECTS

2 students have 57,5 ECTS

1 student has 56 ECTS

1 student has 55 ECTS

1 student has 53 ECTS

1 student was admitted but has 0 ECTS.

1 student dropped out from the start

A5.5. Organized events for the students

Arrival Days; airport pick-up and extra opening hours at KTH Entré, 17 and 18 August

General welcome meetings August 22-23 (general information about KTH, registration)

Program related welcome meeting on August 22, 2024 (information about the SPECTRO program and about courses in the program).

A5.5.1. Career Fair and job market activities

For a number of years, the Degree Project Fair in Kista has been a meeting place for companies and students. From autumn 2025, our students will be taught at the KTH Campus in central Stockholm. One effect of this is that the Degree Project Fair was not organized this year. But there are plenty of other ways to continue strengthening the relationship between KTH and the industry.

A5.5.2. The KTH degree project portal

In addition to the degree project fair once per semester, companies and research groups can advertise their degree projects in KTH's degree project portal all year round. Our sharp students can contribute to solving old problems with new eyes through matching.

[KTH's degree project portal](#)

- Degree Project Portal: [Advertise degree projects](#)
- Advertise permanent positions via [Career Opportunities | Student Union THS](#)
- Contribute with projects in education: [Contribute in education](#)
- Collaborate through person exchanges: [Collaborate with KTH - through person exchanges](#)
- Get involved as an alumnus: [The alumni network](#)
- Find collaborations at KTH: [Find collaborations at KTH](#)
- Subscribe to [mailings from Näringslivssamverkan at KTH](#)

The student union THS and chapters organise various [career days at KTH](#), which are opportunities to meet students. [D-dagen](#), focusing on computer science, and [Potential](#), focusing on electrical engineering, are examples of career days in areas related to education that have been conducted in Kista. The chapters also organise various types of meetings for companies and students. Contact the respective chapter's business groups, for example the [computer chapter](#).

[Contact the Business Relations Group](#) if you have any questions.

Alumni talk video is available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Eiex15UNyi8>

A5.6. Feedback from students

Feedback from students on the courses is positive. Students answered the courses evaluation questionnaires, and their opinion contributed to courses analysis.

Because the questionnaires answers were anonymous (to encourage students to answer freely) it is not possible to separate program students answers from the answers of other students taking the same classes. Typically, program students constitute between 5% and 15% of all students in the class.

A5.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

KTH has marketed SPECTRO as part of the general EIT Digital Master programs. This means that in many ways, they have referred to the EIT Digital website.

This is what is standard for us at KTH:

[Contact us at ICT Innovation \(KTH & EIT Digital\) | Student](#)

A summary of what has been done in terms of communication:

- Master's Fair at KTH
 - ICT Innovation had several tables where all track managers were present to meet students from KTH who might be interested in studying these programs as a focus of their master's programmes
- Webinars
 - [EIT Digital Master School - Autonomous Systems Information Session - 25 January 2024 \(youtube.com\)](#)?Asked for a new if available
 - Tips and tricks to improve your application

- Welcome webinar

The webinars are hosted by staff at KTH but working for the EIT Digital Master School Office.

SPECTRO students recruiting is also driven as part of the total KTH recruitment work inside of EIT ICT Innovation. The calendar of some relevant recruiting activities at KTH for 2024/25 is as follows:

- Welcome meetings August 22-23
- [Newsletters](#), focus opening of application period, events and webinars, student ambassadors, etc.
- Advertising on LinkedIn, Youtube and Google Display (until end of application period)
- Launch [student ambassador interviews and contact form](#) on website, 29 September
- Education and kick-off for all international student ambassadors, 29 September
- Webinar for prospective students " [Explore studies at KTH](#) ", 15 October
- Chat events with KTH staff and student ambassadors with focus on application deadline; 13, 14, 28 January
- FIEP Studies Fair for prospective students in Milan, Italy, 3 March
- Webinar to prospective students "Why choose KTH", 6 March
- Film "Welcome to KTH", 27 March
- Webinar "Admitted! Here's what to do next", 3 April
- Webinar "Your KTH Arrival", 20 May
- Start of recruitment of new international student ambassadors (ISR and Schools)
- Farewell event for international student ambassadors, 5 June

The Master Fair took place on 27 March 2025.

KTH's Civil Engineering students mainly visit the Master's Fair in years 2 and 3, as part of their education, and will study a Master's program. The fair is usually appreciated and well attended, and during the fair, the students have the opportunity to participate in seminars (program presentations) and subsequent question-and-answer sessions.

Time and place for KTH's Master's Fair: 27 March at 15-17 in the Education Building.

A special dissemination activity for SPECTRO is planned during the IEEE COMPSAC 2025 conference to be held in Toronto on July 8-11. We organize the Autonomous Systems symposium as a special track of the COMPSAC. Mihhail Matskin (KTH) is a Chair of the Symposium and most people from SPECTRO Robotics and Autonomous Systems track are members of the Program Committee of the symposium. During the symposium a short presentation of the SPECTRO project will be made. The expected number of participants is about 30 conference attendees.

A5.8. Lesson learned

A general impression about the students and the program organization is quite positive. From the administration point of view everything went smoothly. The program students are well integrated into the educational process at KTH.

Study results of students are in most cases satisfactory. Only 1 student dropped off the program and 1 student did not make any activities in the program. All other students performed well and obtained the required number of credits.

Cooperation with other partners in the project was very good. This includes both development of the program curriculum, student evaluation process and work on organizing the Autonomous Systems symposium at the IEEE COMPSAC 2025 conference.

Some issues and possible improvements can be summarized as follows:

- The Entry year is almost fully packed with compulsory courses and students have the opportunity to take only one elective course. Some comments from students were related to having more opportunities for taking elective courses during the Entry year.
- According to KTH policy students have the right to take any course from KTH as an elective course. We can only provide a list of recommended courses but cannot prevent students from taking any other course. The list of elective courses taken by Entry year students included some courses outside the list of recommended courses, but which are relevant to the program. We plan to modify the list of recommended courses correspondingly.

Student evaluation of the program is done mainly on the course level and because the evaluation of the courses is done anonymously it is impossible to separate answers of the program students from the answers of other students who took the same classes. Making a separate evaluation of particular courses seems to be redundant. We think that it would be useful to have a uniform more program-oriented evaluation which focuses on program organization and its running rather than on evaluation of particular courses.

A6. Université Côte d'Azur (UCA)

Report of activities

A6.1. Classes calendar

Lessons are organized in 2 semesters; exams take place during the semesters (continuous evaluation).

Academic year 2024 - 25

First semester classes: September 3rd, 2024 – January 24th, 2025

Second semester classes: February 3rd, 2025 – May 30th, 2025

A6.2. Enrolled students

For the academic year 2024/25 at UCA, 4 students were enrolled for the Entry Year of the program. Among them 2 are EU nationals and 2 non-EU nationals, 1 woman 3 men.

A6.3. Study plan

UCA offers a study program at Master M1 level in Autonomous Systems. All the fundamental aspects of modeling dynamic systems, parameter and state estimation, control, artificial intelligence and robotics are covered.

ENTRY

LIST OF COURSES: Technical courses (36 ECTS), I&E (24 ECTS)

FIRST SEMESTER

Infotronic (6 ECTS)

- Object-oriented Algorithmic C++
- Embedded Artificial Intelligence

Robotics (6 ECTS)

- Robotics & Sensor Fusion 1 (3 ECTS)
- Autonomous Vehicles (2 ECTS)
- ROS & Gazebo (1 ECTS)

Selected courses (9 ECTS)

- R&D Project S7 (5 ECTS)
- Radio Location Systems (1 ECTS)
- Advanced Tools in Maths and stats (3 ECTS)
- Reinforcement Learning (3 ECTS)
- Embedded Linux (2 ECTS)
- Real-time Operating Systems (2 ECTS)
- Robotics Project (1 ECTS)

Innovation and Entrepreneurship I&E1 (9 ECTS)

- Basics in I&E (3 ECTS)
- Business Intelligence 1 (3 ECTS): Data science for Business
- Business Development Lab 1 (3 ECTS): Project management methods and tools
- Foreign language or Second language (for French speaking students)

SECOND SEMESTER

Autonomy (5 ECTS)

- 3D Machine Vision (2 ECTS)
- Microcontroller Systems (3 ECTS)

Automatic Control (6 ECTS)

- Modeling of Dynamic Systems (1 ECTS)
- Digital Control (4 ECTS)
- Applied Estimation (1 ECTS)

Research and Development Project (4 ECTS)

Elective Innovation and Entrepreneurship I&E (15 ECTS)

- Business Development Lab (5 + 4 ECTS)
- Business Intelligence 2 (3 ECTS): Marketing
- Foreign language or Second language (for French speaking students)
- Innovation & Entrepreneurship complementary course (3 ECTS): Opportunities and Strategy

A6.4. Student Progress

All the students have succeeded in their exams. The two semesters are validated for all 4 students.

A6.5. Organized events for the students

Two welcome events have been organized:

- The first meeting was organized on site at the school Polytech Sophia on Wednesday, September 3rd 2024, where all EIT Digital students were physically present. A presentation was delivered by the AUSIR track coordinator to present the upcoming program and explain logistic matters at school. This was a great opportunity to meet the students in person and help them navigate to find lecture rooms starting on the same day.
 - A Questions & Answers session followed about all possible topics: administrative, accommodation, student card, campus restaurant, location of the lecture rooms and amphitheatres, traveling to university campus, IT, courses agenda, etc. The students really appreciated this first exchange as it allowed us to clarify many points which might have been unclear to them and to remove some anxieties to some of them.
 - A tour of the campus was given.
- The second welcome meeting was organized on September 26th 2024, where all the EIT Digital master students from both UCA and EURECOM (same campus), either entry or exit (Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robotics, FinTech and Data Science), were gathered for an overall presentation followed by a lunch-apéro. All students were pleased to be welcome by the head of the Master school office and very quickly also by the head of EIT Digital education by video conference, by Dr Baude heading EIT Digital activities at UCA and by part of the administrative staff from both UCA and EURECOM taking care of the EIT digital students.

A6.5.1. Career Fair and job market activities

October 15–17, 2024 – Polytech Career Tour: Stages

This is sponsored by Polytech Nice Sophia and aims to connect students with companies. The event offers valuable opportunities to establish contacts with industrial partners for semester projects and internships.

March 6, 2025 – Polytech Career Tour: Forum

The *Career Fair* is organized by Polytech Nice Sophia as a one-day job fair, bringing together numerous companies. It enables students to explore career prospects and see how their academic background aligns with the evolving needs of the labor market.

In addition, UCA students benefit from Polytech Sophia's dedicated office, which supports connections with employers.

An updated list of opportunities is available through the following link, designed to facilitate the matching of students and industry needs: <https://polytechnice.jobteaser.com/fr/>.

A6.6. Feedback from students

Student feedback on the courses has been very favorable. They completed course evaluation surveys, and their input played an important role in assessing the quality of the teaching. At the close of each semester, all SPECTRO students were asked to complete a questionnaire measuring their satisfaction, with a focus on the relevance of course topics, the workload involved, and the suitability of the teaching materials.

A6.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

To better inform students specializing in Robotics Engineering, the program coordinator and the department academic representative organize annual information sessions highlighting the master's programs offered within the department. These events also feature the SPECTRO track in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots, with a focus on international mobility opportunities and dual-degree options through the EIT Digital Master School.

For the 2024/25 academic year, the presentation dedicated to third-year Robotics bachelor students at Polytech was held in January 2025. In addition, the programs are showcased during the annual OPEN DAYS (the 2025 edition took place on February 1st), offering students from pre-master courses as well as external visitors a chance to engage directly with the faculty members responsible for all master's programs.

Beyond these general sessions, a dedicated promotional event for the EIT DIGITAL Master School was delivered in person by Françoise Baude and Jean Pirrodi in spring 2025. This meeting brought together ROBO3 students and all third-year engineering students at Polytech Nice Sophia.

At the same time, UCA has actively promoted the SPECTRO program within the broader framework of the EIT Digital Master initiatives, regularly referring to the EIT Digital website. We have also encouraged our students to attend the EIT Digital webinars designed to guide applicants through the process and strengthen their submissions. These online events, which we advertised through our communication channels, were held on January 28, April 3, and May 15.

On 26/09/2024, Lorenzo FICI, one of our local EIT ambassadors, doing his master thesis at UCA, participated in a communication event at Polytech together with Alexandra Froudikine, where he shared his experience with other students. The related LinkedIn post created at the time is available at the following [LinkedIn Link](#).

Our EIT/SPECTRO ambassador Dalim Whaby, former EIT digital AUS student, who started his PhD at UCA Octobre 1st 2024 has contributed to marketing and dissemination of the SPECTRO education program in the following occasions:

- stay at ETH Zurich Dec. 1st - 4th 2024,
- at 9th IEEE/IFAC International Conference on Control, Automation and Diagnosis (ICCAD), Barcelona, Spain, July 1-3, 2025, where he presented his research article with SPECTRO logo in his slides:

D. Wahby, A. Detailleur, G. Ducard, "Nonlinear Model Reference Adaptive Control (NMRAC) for First-Order Systems," Proceedings of the 9th IEEE/IFAC International Conference on Control, Automation and Diagnosis (ICCAD), Barcelona, Spain, July 1-3, 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCAD64771.2025.11099437>

He met students focusing on Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robotics. These were opportunities to

- present the SPECTRO Master's scholarship, highlighting its relevance and benefits for students interested in pursuing advanced studies in this field.
- raise awareness of SPECTRO's objectives and opportunities

A6.8. Lesson learned

The first year of the Master in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots (SPECTRO track) at UCA was delivered smoothly, with students reporting no difficulty integrating into the university environment. SPECTRO students are mixed with local robotics students and ERASMUS peers, a combination that enriches class dynamics and interaction. Lectures in English and exchanges with international students have also significantly improved local students' language skills. Program coordination at UCA has been effective, with staff and departments working well together. Student support processes have functioned smoothly, and mobility—both incoming and outgoing—has presented no notable challenges. Collaboration with partner universities has also been efficient, ensuring curriculum alignment, coherent assessment, and seamless student progression to the second year.

Industrial partners provide strong added value. Renault Software Lab delivered a full course on “Autonomous Driving,” while STMicroelectronics contributed STM32 development kits with inertial sensors, used in both semester projects. NXP sponsored an AUSIR student team for the “NXP Cup”, supplying hardware for autonomous driving challenges and enabling participation in the international competition.

Two students also conducted a year-long project with ETH Zürich on the control of a two-wheeled inverted pendulum robot (“Sigi”), supported by ETH and UCA researchers.

Overall, student feedback has been highly positive, underlining the program quality and encouraging prospects for SPECTRO. Recruitment for 2025/26 confirms growing interest, with three EU entrants admitted. However, the low proportion of female students highlights the need for targeted measures to address gender imbalance.

A7. University of Bologna (UNIBO)

Report of activities

The first year of the program has started in 2024/25 as part of the international second-cycle (Master's) degree in Automation Engineering. The degree is part of the School of Engineering within the Department of Electrical, Electronic and Information Engineering.

AUSIR Academic Coordinator and degree coordinator: Giuseppe Notarstefano

Programme (administrative) coordinator: Francesca Franchi

A7.1. Classes calendar

The academic year at University of Bologna is organized in two semesters (lecture cycles) scheduled according to the following calendar.

Academic Calendar A.Y. 2024/25

Lectures

1st period: from 16 September 2024 to 20 December 2024.

2nd period: from 17 February 2025 to 13 June 2025.

Exam sessions:

1st period: from 23 December 2024 to 14 February 2025.

2nd period: from 16 June 2025 to 12 September 2025.

A7.2. Enrolled students

In the cohort 2024/25 there were 8 enrolled students in the AUSIR program. They were split as follows:

ENTRY STUDENTS: 6 students (all male, 1 non-EU)

EXIT STUDENTS: 2 students (1 male and 1 female, all EU)

The 6 entry students have regularly enrolled, attended the course lectures according to the study plan and started to take the exams.

A7.3. Study plan

The first year of Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots (AUSIR) - SPECTRO study programme, consistently with the agreed common structure reported in deliverable D2.1, covers technical courses in Robotics, AI, modelling, estimation and control together with Innovation and Entrepreneurship (I&E) courses. The detailed course structure diagram is reported below.

The implemented 2024/25 course structure diagram is as follows.

First semester

Compulsory Course (9 ECTS)

- System Theory and Advanced Control

Elective courses

Select 15 ECTS total in first or second semester to cover Mechanics area (9ECTS) and Computer Engineering area (6 ECTS)

- Modelling and Simulation of Mechatronic Systems (mod.1)
- Image Processing and Computer Vision
- Operating Systems and programming for Automation

I&E (14 ECTS)

- Project Management and Entrepreneurship M
- Resources and Production Optimization (Integrated course): Resources Optimization

Second semester

Compulsory Courses (12 ECTS)

- Industrial Robotics
- Learning and Estimation of Dynamical Systems

Elective courses

Select 15 ECTS total in first or second semester to cover Mechanics area (9ECTS) and Computer Engineering area (6 ECTS)

- Modelling and Simulation of Mechatronic Systems (mod.2)
- Mechanics of Machines for Automation
- Optimization and Machine Learning

I&E (10 ECTS)

- Resources and Production Optimization (Integrated course): Production Management and Optimization
- Summer School

A7.4. Student Progress

The 6 students enrolled in the first year have attended the mandatory courses and have chosen elective ones according to their personal study plan.

Number of credits completed in average: 46.5 as per August 2025

Out of the 6 enrolled students, 5 students are on track (with 51 credits completed on average), while 1 student has opted for a one-year leave of study between the first and second year.

A7.5. Organized events for the students

The tutors of Automation Engineering, welcoming and supporting students in their academic life have also supported SPECTRO students. Considering the limited number of SPECTRO students and the new program, the degree coordinator and the administrative program coordinator have interacted directly with the SPECTRO students to support them in the degree procedures and interactions with EIT and with the exit universities.

A dedicated meeting was organized by the coordinator of the Automation Engineering degree for the SPECTRO students. The students were welcomed in the SPECTRO program and instructions were given together with suggestions on the courses of the first semester and possible choices of elective courses. An overview of the teaching and evaluation procedures have been given to the students with particular suggestions to students coming from a different university. The administrative program coordinator gave students all the necessary information on administrative deadlines and procedures for the study plan and the taxes. In particular, regarding the taxes, the students were informed that some procedures were still under definition with EIT. In the subsequent weeks a continuous interaction with students has been active until the tax procedure was successfully ended.

A7.5.1. Career Fair and job market activities

On May 15th Automation Engineering students (included AUSIR ones) joined the SPS Italia - Smart Production Solutions fair. The fair is one of the most important national events on Automation and offers students the possibility to get in contact with the main Automation companies and have an idea of advanced technologies.

A7.6. Feedback from students

The SPECTRO students, being part of a UNIBO degree, have answered to the questionnaires about the quality of each teaching course. The questionnaires are anonymous and are used by the Quality Assurance committee of the degree to monitor the activities. The Automation Engineering degree has shown overall very positive scores, which suggests that also the SPECTRO students were satisfied by the program.

This was confirmed by an ad-hoc interaction with the SPECTRO students. The students were asked via email to give their feedback on the first semester. They highlighted some difficulties mainly due to taxes procedures (which then have been solved) and visa delays for foreign students. Besides that, they were mostly satisfied of the program in general. At the end of the second semester there was another interaction with the students. The feedback was positive in terms of topics and organization of the courses. Some students showed a particular appreciation for the organization and structure of the I&E courses and suggested to shift it also to some technical courses. As a further suggestion, students asked to better organize the period of the summer schools to avoid overlapping with the local exam period. This will be taken into account for the next year in discussions with the project partners.

A7.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

The website of Automation Engineering includes a dedicated page on the SPECTRO double degree programme in which potential candidates can find all the required information and links for the application process. Moreover, in the "Course Structure Diagram" page a dedicated page is reserved to the SPECTRO double degree with the study plan.

UNIBO supports the promotion of AUSIR through its network, communication channels, and events. As part of the Master's Degree in Automation Engineering, the program can benefit from the comprehensive communication strategy at the University of Bologna to highlight its international academic offerings. Every year, the University of Bologna undertakes various actions to provide prospective students with information about its international degrees.

AUSIR has been actively promoted during the following online events:

1. **"International Open Days"** (November 26, 2024 – December 6 2024). In particular, on November 27, 2024 it took place the online event for the presentation of the Master's Degrees belonging to the Electrical, Electronic and Information Engineering area, Results: 120 have registered students to join the event with about 38% from abroad.

2. **"Unibo Orientation Days"** which is the main fair providing an overview of Master's Degrees taught in English (February 26, 2025).

The event was held online, and the Automation Engineering booth saw the participation of 698 (165 Master and 533 Bachelor). Within the framework of the fair, a dedicated informative session on the

AUSIR Programme was conducted both for Bachelor's and Master's prospects in order to inform students about this notable opportunity.

Furthermore, opportunities were provided for interaction between current students enrolled in the AUSIR Programme/Phd students in Automation and potential ones through initiatives such as "student cafe" and guided tours of the laboratories of Robotics and Complex Automated Systems. According to the collected feedback, the student cafe and the online visits to the labs were especially appreciated by participants, highlighting the value of hands-on exposure to the facilities. Moreover, the opportunity to engage with "peers" such as current students it has been proved to be highly informative and involving.

3. Department Open days (both live and online) on November 8, 2024 and April 16, 2025 dedicated to potential bachelor students. In the presentation of the bachelor program the SPECTRO project with the AUSIR program was advertised as a potential follow up and international initiative.

4. Specific info sessions (in class and by email) for prospective Automation Engineering students promoting the AUSIR track have also been implemented throughout the year. It is important to note that the Master's Degree in Automation Engineering is a well-established program with a strong international dimension and appeal, attracting over 100 enrolled students per year and showing a growing trend of applications (nearly 2000 per year).

Additionally, AUSIR (as a track of the Master's Degree in Automation Engineering) has benefited of the marketing actions implemented by the Unibo Guidance services.

A digital advertising campaign on Google and Meta has been organized from March 24 to June 22, 2025 addressed both to EU and NON-EU students. The Degree Programme was promoted through posts and ads on Google and Meta containing keywords. They anchor a landing page reporting a short programme profile and redirect to the Degree Programme website.

Hereafter the detailed outcomes of such communication activities:

-the Google ads campaign has achieved 21.651 impressions and 1998 click, whereas the one on Meta has reached 363.475 impressions and 15.323 click.

Moreover, the access statistics to landing page describing the master's degree programme show over 5,221 visits and 235 clicks to the degree programme websites. A significant proportion of these visits are from Indonesia (at about 23%) followed by Colombia, Turkey and Romania.

International Degree Programmes of the University of Bologna have also been promoted online through the Education.com Portal managed by the Keystone education group. This platform enables Universities to provide a brief description of their degree programmes and prospects to ask for supplementary information through a form (admission, tuition fees etc).

This communication campaign has spanned one year from August 1 2024 to July 31, 2025.

The Keystone Performance Report shows the following data about the master's degree in Automation Engineering in the considered time frame:

-62540 impressions as views on program listing pages
-729 clicks on the programme profile
-89 *student leads* as those who successfully submitted the enquiry form to request more information about the program. 86% of students who have contacted the degree programme were male and they plan to apply for admission within 6-12 months.

SPECTRO project activities have been disseminated during the advertising events and campaigns for students' enrollment. The ongoing project activities and results have been presented with the successful stories.

A7.8. Lesson learned

This is the first year for the SPECTRO Programme and the University of Bologna did not have previous experience with double degrees including EIT and its partner universities. Thus, the kickoff was challenging due to several administration constraints that required a strong negotiation with EIT Digital and within different areas of the University of Bologna for the implementation of the program. In particular, the tuition fees policy (including deduction/full and half waiver scholarships) and the enrollment process have posed issues that however have then been smoothly solved.

Engagement of AUSIR students has shown that (even) within the UNIBO bachelor program there were several students interested in a double degree program giving the possibility to spend one year in a prestigious foreign university. Moreover, the particular structure of the AUSIR program (including AI-related topics and the I&E minor) has attracted students from other bachelor programs, such as students from Computer Engineering.

The local Teaching Committee of the Master's Degree in Automation Engineering (including professors of the Automation Engineering degree) performed the evaluation of the candidates according to the admission criteria of the Automation Engineering program. The admin programme coordinator (Dr. Francesca Franchi) has been supporting prospective students providing information about the program and the required documents for the admission as well as enrolled students throughout their academic career. The special structure of the program including interaction with EIT Digital and with multiple university was a peculiar feature of this program and required interaction with other partners. Yet, thanks to the very collaborative spirit of the consortium the (minor) admin doubts were smoothly solved.

The interactions and communication with the programme lead was carried out by the Degree director Prof. Giuseppe Notarstefano in collaboration with Dr. Francesca Franchi (admin support of the Degree Programme) together with professors of the Quality Assurance Committee and with the partnerships for education division of the University of Bologna. The experience of other partners within the program gave the possibility to share useful ideas for the whole program.

The enrolled students in the AUSIR program choosing UNIBO as one of the options went beyond the expectations and the trend seems to be confirmed also in the second recruiting year. Also, the positive experience of the enrolled students regarding the overall program initiatives and the quality of the UNIBO courses (first year) is encouraging for the follow up of the SPECTRO project.

A8. University of Trento (UNITN)

Report of activities

A8.1. Classes calendar

Lessons are organized in 2 semesters followed by exam sessions.

Academic year 2024/25

First semester classes: 23 September 2024 – 20 December 2024

National Holiday: 1 November, Christmas Holidays from 23 December 2024 to 6 January 2025

Exam period: 7 January- 21 February 2025

Second semester classes: 24 February 2025 - 6 June 2025

National Holiday: 18 April, 21 April 2025, 1 May and 2 May 2025, 2 June 2025

Exam period: 9 June 2025- 31 July 2025

Re-exam period: 25 August- 9 September 2025

A8.2. Enrolled students

For the academic year 2024/25 in UNITN we enrolled 8 students for the Entry Year of the program and 3 for the Exit Year. Among them 9 are EU nationals and 2 non-EU nationals. Also 4 of the admitted students are females and 7 are males. There are two requests of Leave of Study for this academic year, these two students will be back next September.

A8.3. Study plan

The set of courses for Entry students in 2024/25 is completely compliant with the list of courses presented in the Annex in 2.1.

ENTRY YEAR	60 ECTS
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FIRST SEMESTER			27 ECTS
Compulsory courses			15 ECTS
Robotic perception and action		9	
Machine learning		6	

Electives courses			0 ECTS
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I&E			12 ECTS
Digital production and logistics systems			
- Mod.1 - Design of digital production and assembly systems (6 ECTS)		6	
- Mod.2 - Logistics and warehouse management		6	

SECOND SEMESTER			33 ECTS
Compulsory courses			15 ECTS
Modeling and simulation of mechatronic systems		9	
Automatic control		6	

Electives courses (one from the list below)			6 ECTS
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I&E			12 ECTS
Business development laboratory		9	
Summer school		3+1	

List of Electives courses	Semester		
Quality and innovation engineering	2	6	
Design methods for unmanned vehicles	2	6	
Computer vision	2	6	
Deep learning	2	6	
Laboratory of the Internet of Things	2	6	
Introduction to robotics	2	6	

EXIT YEAR (60 ECTS)	60 ECTS
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FIRST SEMESTER			30 ECTS
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Compulsory courses			18 ECTS
Distributed robot perception		6	
Intelligent vehicles and autonomous driving		6	
Robot planning and its applications		6	

Electives courses (one from the list below)			6 ECTS
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I&E			6 ECTS
Innovation and entrepreneurship studies in ICT		6	

SECOND SEMESTER			30 ECTS
Master thesis project			30 ECTS
(internship + Thesis)			

List of Electives courses	Semester		
Embedded systems	2	6	
Advanced Formula SAE	2	6	
Renewable energy conversion systems	2	6	
Robot planning and its applications	2	6	
Industrial robotics	2	6	
Advanced optimization-based robot control	2	6	
Project course	2	6	

Comments (if any):
The Summer School provides 4 ECTS, and 3ECTS are enough for the program in UNITN. The Master thesis project includes a mandatory internship in a company.

A8.4. Student Progress

At the time of writing this report, the examination session is still in progress, and thus we do not possess a comprehensive overview. In any case, 7 students have passed three or four exams, and only one student has not obtained any credits.

A8.5. Organized events for the students

In order to greet the SPECTRO students, we have arranged a dedicated Welcome Day in the first week of lessons, on 23 September 2024, with the SPECTRO coordinators in UNITN and our Welcome Office for information about UNITN services.

The Department of Industrial Engineering presented a series of thematic seminars dedicated to "Architectures of Intelligent Transportation Systems" organized by Prof. Gastone Rosati Papini.

From May 6th to May 22nd, leading experts shared their knowledge on string stability, advanced simulation, V2X communication, and the state of the art of autonomous vehicles.

That was an unmissable opportunity for our students to delve into the technologies that are transforming the way we travel. Presented below is the Seminar Schedule:

06/05 - String stability of car-following models Prof. Marcello Montanino - University of Napoli (online)

08/05 - Simulation in V-Cycle and Continuous Validation Christian Pagliara - Soluzioni ingegneria

20/05 - Vehicle-to-Everything Communication (V2X) for ADAS Filippo Visintainer Technical Fellow - CRF (Centro ricerche Fiat)

22/05 - Automated Vehicles State of Play & Future Outlook Riccardo Donà Project Officer - European Commission

A8.5.1. Career Fair and job market activities

13 November 2024 Industrial Engineering Day

Industrial Engineering Day is the event sponsored by the Department of Industrial Engineering to bring its students together with companies. In the 2024 edition 33 companies participated to the event.

14 May 2025 Career Fair

The Career Fair is a job fair organized by Job Guidance in collaboration with UniTrento's Departments, Centers and Schools to offer the opportunity to meet different companies in a single day in job fair mode and understand how one's course of study can intersect with the demands of an increasingly demanding job market. For 2025, the event took place on May 14 at the Trento Expo. All lessons are suspended and all students are invited to participate.

Additionally, SPECTRO students can take advantage of the UNITN office dedicated to connecting with the job market. The UNITN Job Guidance's website features internship opportunities and job offers, allowing students to engage with the business world. This is the link where you can check the constantly updated proposals to help match supply and demand.

<https://www.jobguidance.unitn.it/en>

A8.6. Feedback from students

Students' feedback on the courses has been largely positive. They participated in the course evaluation questionnaires, and their opinions significantly contributed to the analysis of the courses.

At the end of the first semester, we sent a questionnaire to all SPECTRO students to assess their satisfaction, focusing on their interest in the topics offered in the courses, the workload required, and whether the teaching materials were appropriate.

A8.7. Marketing, recruiting and dissemination activities

In a targeted effort to guide students in the Mechatronics Engineering course, the program coordinator and the department's educational delegate arrange annual meetings to present the master's degree programs available in the department. These sessions also cover the SPECTRO program in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots, including its international mobility options for dual degrees through the EIT Digital Master School.

For the academic year 2024/25, the presentation event, which is exclusively for third-year students enrolled in the bachelor's degree in Industrial Engineering, occurred in December 2024. Furthermore, the degree program is introduced during the OPEN DAYS for Master's Degrees held by the University of Trento each spring (the 2025 edition took place on April 17): this is an opportunity for interaction with the faculty responsible for all Master's degree programs in the department, aimed at both students from the bachelor's program and any external interested individuals.

Besides these general presentations aimed at our undergraduate students, a specific promotional meeting for the EIT DIGITAL Master School courses was held in person on March, 18th.

<https://eventi.unitn.it/it/eit-digital-master-school-byte-slice>

Additionally, UNITN has promoted SPECTRO within the broader EIT Digital Master programs. This indicates that they have frequently referenced the EIT Digital website.

We have also encouraged our students to participate in the webinars organized by EIT Digital aimed at providing tips to enhance and finalize their applications. Consequently, we promoted these events on our channels, which took place on January 28, April 3, and May 15.

IMDEA Networks (Leganés, Madrid) invited Prof. Davide Brunelli (University of Trento) to deliver a seminar aimed at bachelor students, focusing on current trends in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robotics. The seminar was scheduled on April 10 and held in person at IMDEA Networks, also served as an opportunity to present the SPECTRO Master's scholarship, highlighting its relevance and benefits for students interested in pursuing advanced studies in this field. The event fostered dialogue

around potential academic collaboration between the involved institutions and helped raise awareness of SPECTRO's objectives and opportunities among a new generation of researchers.

IMDEA Networks (Leganés, Madrid) is actively engaged in following the developments of the European Union's initiative, with particular interest in its applications to autonomous systems and intelligent robotics.

A8.8. Lesson learned

After an extensive preparation period, the delivery of the first year of the Master in Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots, as part of SPECTRO, has been successful and smooth at UNITN. The enrolled students have seamlessly integrated into our university's environment and have shown appreciation for the proposed organization.

Moreover, the presence of the SPECTRO student group, which includes international students with diverse backgrounds, adds significant value to the lessons.

The internal coordination among the UNITN staff engaged in the management of the SPECTRO programme, as well as the faculty from the two departments involved in the AUSIR (specifically, the Department of Industrial Engineering and the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science), has been productive and well-coordinated. In September, we convened a meeting to discuss communication about the SPECTRO programme, bringing together the relevant offices to harmonize efforts between the two departments and to promote the dissemination campaigns. The student organization at UNITN has shown to be effective, and both incoming and outgoing students do not appear to encounter any particular challenges with this.

Collaboration with other partners in the project was highly effective. This encompasses the development of the programme curriculum and the student evaluation process, both during recruitment and in grade conversion.

The interaction with the administrative departments of other universities has been fluid and uninterrupted, enabling students to move into their second year without facing challenges.

The recruitment process for the 2025/26 cohort has revealed the growing attractiveness of Robotics, as the number of students who accepted the study offer has risen.

For the academic year 2025/26, UNITN will admit 11 Entry students, 9 of whom are EU nationals, the primary target of the SPECTRO programme. Only one of these students is female, which leads us to believe that additional measures are necessary to address this gender gap. For the Exit Year, UNITN will welcome 4 students (2 EU and 2 non-EU), which is an increase of one unit compared to the previous year.

A9. Company name: GIM Robotics

A9.1. SPECTRO-related activities from GIM Robotics

A9.1.1. Lectures:

- **13.03.2024 EUROPEAN ROBOTICS FORUM, RIMINI, ITALY**
Organizer: University of Bologna (with other organizers)
Event: European Robotics Forum 2024
Title: “FUTURE WORKSITES – from academic demonstrations to real-world implementations”
Lecturer: Dr. Mika Vainio
- **26.03.2024 AALTO UNIVERSITY, ESPOO, FINLAND**
Course: ELEC-E8111 - Autonomous Mobile Robots
Professor: Tomasz Piotr Kucner, Department of Electrical Engineering and Automation
Title: “ROS as an enabler: from Finnish center of excellence to global field and service robotics markets”
Lecturer: Dr. Mika Vainio
- **28.04.2024 UNIVERSITY OF TURKU, TURKU, FINLAND**
Course: KTEK0054 - Robotics
Professor: Dr. Jani Heikkinen, Dept of Mechanical and Materials Engineering
Title: “Full stack automation software working in all weather conditions with centimeter-level positioning”
Lecturer: Dr. Mika Vainio
- **30.09.2024 AALTO UNIVERSITY, ESPOO, FINLAND,**
Course: MEC-E5012 - Vehicle Mechatronics: Control
Professor: Risto Ojala, Department of Energy and Mechanical Engineering
Title: “GIM Robotics – from academic demonstrations to real-world implementations”
Lecturer: Dr. Mika Vainio
- **22.10.2024 AI DAY, HELSINKI, FINLAND**
Organizer: [Finnish Center for Artificial Intelligence FCAI](#) (including Aalto University)
Event: AI DAY is the largest annual gathering of AI researchers in the Nordics
Title: “Success Factors for Industry-Academia Collaboration”
Lecturer: Dr. Jose Luis Peralta (with Prof. Ville Kyrki, Aalto University)
- **11.04.2025 UNIVERSITY OF TURKU, TURKU, FINLAND**
Course: KTEK0054 - Robotics
Professor: Dr. Jani Heikkinen, Dept of Mechanical and Materials Engineering / Professor Tomi Westerlund, Turku Intelligent Embedded and Robotics Systems (TIERS) lab
Title: “GIM Robotics – from Uni to Biz”

Lecturer: Dr. Mika Vainio

A9.1.2. Other participation (in 2025) and contributions

1. General Assembly (short GIM Robotics Intro: **Utilizing Academic Results in a Commercial Setting**, (27.2.2025), Biot, France
2. Interim review meeting with the European Commission (26-27.3.2025), Budapest, Hungary
3. Spectro, material for EIT-Digital marketing people, 15.4.2025:

THE GIMSTERS IN SPECTRO. Abstract. Being asked to join a prestigious group of universities as the only robotics company was a real honour to all of us in GIM Robotics. We became involved in SPECTRO through our close links with Aalto University, our alma mater, and its active participation in EIT Digital's activities. Now we have a chance to transfer our knowledge to the next generation of robotics engineers. We owe that to them. (See the text at the end)

News (by Mr. Guerrini, EIT-Digital):

Voices from SPECTRO: GIM Robotics brings industry expertise to European robotics Education

Read here: <https://www.eitdigital.eu/newsroom/news/2025/voices-from-spectro-gim-robotics-brings-industry-expertise-to-european-robotics-education/>

4. The Ecosystem: EIT Digital recruits companies to stay ahead of the skills curve
(10 Oct 2023) <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/universities/ecosystem-eit-digital-recruits-companies-stay-ahead-skills-curve>
5. News on GIM Robotics' website: <https://gimrobotics.fi/spectro-specialised-education-programmes-in-cybersecurity-and-robotics/>
6. LinkedIn posts: 3.6.2025 and 28.4.2025

A10. University of the Aegean (AEGEAN)

Report of activities

A10.1. Initial engagement

The first contact with the AUSIR coordination team came through Dr. Sergio Balassone, who introduced the idea of extending the Summer School on Maritime Informatics & Robotics into a specialization track within the AUSIR double degree program. This provided an opportunity to build on UoA's established strengths in maritime informatics, digital innovation, and robotics education.

Based on this initial exchange, the University of the Aegean (UAEGEAN) prepared a proposal highlighting its capabilities in the field of maritime informatics, autonomous systems, and data-driven engineering, as well as its unique advantage of operating an on-water testbed in Syros for real-world experimentation. The proposal included UoA's commitment and capacity to host the second year (Exit University) of the program, with a strong emphasis on practical and experimental training in maritime robotics.

Following a positive evaluation, UAEGEAN was formally included as an Exit University, with the first incoming AUSIR students expected to arrive in the autumn of 2026, starting their studies in the first semester of the 2026/2027 academic year.

The implementation agreement was formally established in 2025 through a departmental approval process. The local AUSIR academic team submitted a formal request to the Department Council of the Department of Product & Systems Design Engineering, which endorsed the proposal. The decision was subsequently approved by the Academic Senate of the University of the Aegean, confirming the institution's full participation in AUSIR.

This structured approach ensured both compliance with internal governance procedures and alignment with national requirements, setting the foundation for the smooth integration of AUSIR students into the University's academic environment.

A10.2. Promotion and Initial Activities

In the initial months of involvement, UAEGEAN initiated targeted promotional activities to raise awareness of AUSIR among local and regional students.

The program was presented during departmental and faculty information sessions, with a particular focus on students enrolled in the Bachelor's degrees of the Polytechnic School:

- Department of Product and Systems Design Engineering (Syros),
- Department of Information and Communication Systems Engineering (Samos), and
- Department of Financial and Management Engineering (Chios)

These outreach activities emphasized the benefits of AUSIR as a transnational, double-degree opportunity, highlighting UoA's specialization track in Maritime Informatics & Robotics.

The University also leveraged its international collaborations and networks (e.g., through EIT Digital and ongoing Horizon Europe projects) to promote AUSIR as part of a broader ecosystem of European education and research in autonomy, data, and robotics.

Although the program is in its preparatory phase, UAEGEAN has already received positive expressions of interest from both undergraduate students and external applicants who view the maritime robotics specialization as a unique educational pathway.

Finally, as per Greek higher education regulations, all new MSc programs must be certified by the National Authority for Higher Education (EΘAEE). The AUSIR program is currently in the certification process, and UAEGEAN staff is actively coordinating with EΘAEE to secure the required accreditation in time for the 2026/2027 intake.

This careful combination of promotion, academic integration, and regulatory alignment ensures that UAEGEAN is well-prepared to deliver its role as an Exit University in AUSIR.

A11. Polytechnic University of Bari

Report of activities

A11.1. Initial Engagement

The first contact between the Polytechnic University of Bari (POLIBA) and the AUSIR coordination team occurred in early August 2024, through Dr. Salvatore Moccia. His guidance was instrumental in efficiently navigating the proposal process for joining the AUSIR double degree master program.

With his support, POLIBA submitted its proposal in the first half of October 2024, focusing on the specialization track titled “*Aeronautical Robotics & More Electrical Aircrafts.*” The proposal outlined our capabilities and interest in hosting the second year (Exit University) of the program.

Following a positive evaluation, POLIBA was formally included as an Exit University, with the first incoming AUSIR students expected to arrive in the autumn of 2026, starting the first semester of the 2026/2027 academic year.

The implementation agreement was formally established in March 2025 through a departmental approval process. The local AUSIR academic team submitted a formal request to the Department Council of the involved department, i.e., the Department of Electrical and Information Engineering (DEI). The Council unanimously approved POLIBA’s participation in the AUSIR program. This method was intentionally chosen to streamline internal procedures and avoid delays commonly associated with approval by Academic Senate or University Executive Board. This faster, yet fully compliant, process could serve as a “lesson learned” and a viable approach for future Italian universities aiming to join the program under similar conditions.

A11.2. Promotion and Initial Activities

In the initial months of involvement, POLIBA launched preliminary promotional efforts, primarily targeting local students. The AUSIR program was introduced and discussed with students enrolled in our Bachelor’s programs, particularly:

- the BSc in Aerospace Systems Engineering
- the BSc in Computer and Automation Engineering

These activities were aimed at raising awareness about the opportunities of an international double-degree track, as well as POLIBA's role as a host institution for the second year of specialization.

Despite being in a preparatory phase, POLIBA has already received multiple expressions of interest and applications from students aiming to join the AUSIR program and identifying POLIBA as a potential Exit University.

A total of eight applications were reviewed in this early period:

- 4 applicants selected POLIBA as their first choice
- 3 as their second choice
- 1 as their third choice

The evaluation process was conducted thoroughly by the local AUSIR academic reference team. The academic background and motivation of the applicants were carefully assessed, and overall, we found the quality of applications satisfactory and promising. This positive response reinforces our motivation to continue promoting the program and engaging with the international AUSIR student community.